

**Between Nations and Empires.
Esperanto in Poland, 1887-1939.**

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Declarations

Candidate's declaration:

I, Nina Walter, hereby certify that this thesis, which is approximately 25,000 words in length, has been written by me, and that it is the record of work carried out by me, or principally by myself in collaboration with others as acknowledged, and that it has not been submitted in any previous application for a higher degree.

I was admitted as a research student at the University of St Andrews as a candidate for the degree of Master of Studies (Research) History in September 2019.

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I hereby certify that the candidate has fulfilled the conditions of the Resolution and Regulations appropriate for the degree of Master of Studies (Research) in the University of St Andrews and that the candidate is qualified to submit this thesis in application for that degree.

Date *24.10.2020*

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Abstract

Esperanto is a universal language created in 1887 by Ludwik Zamenhof, a Warsaw-based Jewish ophthalmologist and language enthusiast. Although born in Poland, the Esperanto movement in the country has not been given enough attention by existing research. This thesis was written to fill the existing research gap in the subject, to analyse the historical context of the spread of Esperanto on the Polish territories, its main actors, and the role it played in Poland before the outbreak of World War II. The thesis asks questions as to how and why the reception of Esperanto changed throughout the years and contextualises the Polish Esperanto movement in contemporary Europe. The thesis argues that the reception and development of the Esperanto movement in Poland was directly correlated with the socio-political situation of the country during the partitions and later, after regaining independence in 1918. As opposed to more established European nation-states at the time, Esperanto in Poland was used by the intellectual and professional elites of the country to promote the new nation abroad and form transnational networks to accelerate the country's progress. At the same time, Esperanto was criticised in the re-emerging state, with its ideology of tolerance and common humanity transcending national borders seen as a direct danger to the long fought for version of Polishness. Most importantly, however this thesis serves as a springboard for future research of Esperanto and nationalism, an area underexplored by researchers, who tend to focus on the a-national aspects of the movement.

Key words: Esperanto, Poland, Pola Esperantisto, universal language, Esperanto movement, interwar, partitioned, Zamenhof.

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INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

There is a Zamenhof Street in my hometown, Przemyśl. One of the shortest in town, always made me wonder who this Zamenhof actually was. While the etymology of the surrounding streets would be pretty clear to any Polish schoolchild: Mickiewicz was the great bard, Copernicus moved the Earth and the Home Army are our never forgotten heroes, I scratched my head about this one. Ludwik Lejzer Zamenhof was never mentioned in any class, never included in the canon of “the Great Poles” and national heroes, and Esperanto, the language invented by him, meant nothing more to me than a crossword entry.

Today, it seems that Esperanto has been almost completely wiped out from the collective Polish memory. It could be argued that apart from a few brief mentions in local papers, on occasions such as the unveiling of Zamenhof’s monument in his native Białystok,¹ or street naming, Ludwik Lazar Zamenhof hardly makes headlines these days. Despite the efforts of a handful of die-hard Esperanto enthusiasts from the Polish Esperanto Association and “Varsovia Vento”, an informal Esperanto club I had a chance to visit in their makeshift allotment house-turned-Esperanto temple during my stay in Warsaw, Esperanto remains widely unknown in Zamenhof’s homeland and there seems to be too little interest in it, or funding from the government and the EU², to change it.

¹ ”Powstał pomnik młodego Zamenhofa,” *Gazeta Wyborcza Białystok*, 11th April 2019.

² Pola Esperanto-Junularo, ”Statut Polskiego Związku Esperantystów” <<http://pej.pl/pl/o-nas/dokumenty/statut-polskiego-zwiazku-esperantystow/>>.

This begs a number of questions that this thesis addresses: was Esperanto just a temporary fad, which, in today's terms, went viral for some time, had its five minutes of fame, and then disappeared into thin air only to be replaced by newer trends? Did it bear absolutely no significance to the Polish state or nationhood, or at least was its influence so minimal that it is not even worth a mention? Who was Zamenhof and what was his attitude to Poland and the language he created? Who were the early Esperantists and what motivated them to learn this strange, new language? What gaps and needs did Esperanto manage to fill, both in the pre-independent country striving to define itself and in the post 1918 reborn nation? What was the general attitude to Zamenhof and Esperanto in its peak years during the early twentieth century? What was the Esperantists' attitude to Poland?

In this thesis, I will be trying to engage with these (and more) questions. This research project will portray the background and the *Zeitgeist* of the years that provided fertile ground to the Polish Esperanto movement. It will mainly focus on the years between its creation in 1887 (the official publication date of Zamenhof's *Unua Libro*, the first ever introduction to Esperanto) and the outbreak of the Second World War, which marked the end of the Second Polish Republic. I will try to analyse the relationship between Poland and Esperanto and ask questions about the role it played there in the timeframe specified above. Most importantly, however, I will seek to fill the vacuum created by the paradoxical lack of input from a wide array of historians describing this otherwise widely covered period in the Polish history.

1.2 Historiography and secondary literature

Historical works on Poland usually feature lists of Yiddish, Polish, Russian or German newspapers, percentages and proportions between different ethnicities, numbers of synagogues and churches of different denominations. Yet, only a few historians go deeper into the subject of linguistic diversity and relationships between languages in the pre-WW2 Poland and occupied Polish territories before 1918. In other words, history does not always tell us how people talked to one another in the times when (partitioned) Poland was one of the most diverse regions in Europe. One could go as far as to say that people these days do not realise how colourful and unique the situation was at the time in terms of linguistic, cultural, religious diversity.

Indeed, at some point in history the region of so-called Eastern Borderlands created not only multi-ethnic but also multilingual families. One notable case includes the prominent Szeptycki family, where two brothers, one a general in Polish Army, another head of Greek Orthodox Church, could not agree on the language of their official meeting, and as a result chose to hold the talks in French, and not Polish or Ukrainian³.

This presents us with a situation of cultural and linguistic “third space” in Homi Bhabha’s terms: a hybrid situation, where cultures, languages and traditions overlap. The “third space” is often the result of social inequalities and different cultural standards and, as such, creates a space where “hierarchical claims to the inherent originality or ‘purity’ of cultures are untenable”⁴. This was certainly the case in both occupied and newly independent Poland, a “melting pot” of

³ Hanna Komorowska, “Analyzing Linguistic Landscapes. A Diachronic Study of Multilingualism in Poland”. *Teaching and Learning in Multilingual contexts: Sociolinguistic and Educational Perspectives*, Eds. Otwinowska, A. and de Angelis, G. (Bristol: Multilingual Matters, 2014), p. 22.

⁴ Homi Bhabha, *The Location of Culture* (New York: Routledge, 1994), p. 55.

Europe at the time. Yet the topic has not been explored enough and the ethnic and linguistic breakdown of the Second Polish Republic is often presented in very segregated, black and white terms, without any attempt to take a closer look at the complexity of linguistic relationships and identities. It is therefore hardly surprising that none of the major chroniclers, such as Norman Davies, Jędrzej Giertych, Marian Kamil Dziewanowski, Jan Karski, or Piotr Wandycz even mention Esperanto in their works. While all of them provide ample record of multiculturalism in the years leading up to independence and the second Polish Republic (and prior), hardly anyone focuses their lens on multilingualism. The cultural diversity of the region is presented rather as a source of conflict, especially by the right-wing Giertych. In his *In Defence of My Country*, he mostly blames Jews for choosing to speak Russian, “the language which the Poles hated and boycotted”⁵, over Polish, in the times of partition. As one might expect from a deeply nationalistic historian, an attempt to build linguistic and interpersonal bridges between peoples has no place in a “national” history.

Dziewanowski in his *Poland in the twentieth century* again focuses more on ethnic, rather than linguistic diversity, though at least he does mention various contributions of the ethnic minorities to the Polish economy and culture.⁶ Norman Davies, however, in his book *God's Playground. A History of Poland*, again segregates all the ethnicities inhabiting the Polish territories into separate slices, as dutifully illustrated by his pie charts. He, as well as the others, sees Poles only from an ethnic perspective, highlighting differences between various groups and with an astonishing ease, giving them colourful but rather judgemental labels, such as “pauperized

⁵ Jędrzej Giertych, *In Defence of My Country* (London: Publications of the Roman Dmowski Society, 1981), p. 259.

⁶ Marian Kamil Dziewanowski, *Poland in the twentieth century* (New York: Columbia University Press, 1977), ps. 88-89.

proletariat “ or “rich professionals” in case of Jews, “small but relatively wealthy bourgeoisie” for Germans, or “poor, illiterate peasants” for the Ukrainians.⁷ Indeed, he presents other ethnic groups as a threat to Polish nationalism, presenting them as “fundamentally incompatible with the aim of national unity as conceived by government Polish circles”.⁸ Nowhere in his great opus on Polish history does he even attempt to give some insight into the intricate identities on the Polish territories in the first decades of the 20th century.

The cardinal literature of the subject is strangely silent on Esperanto in Poland. It is barely mentioned anywhere, if not to say overlooked and dismissed as the origin of the language. Despite Ludwik Zamenhof calling himself “the son of Poland”⁹, his Polish connection is very often minimized. Alexander Korzhenkov, in his biography of Zamenhof, calls him “a Russian Jew” born in Russian Białystok¹⁰, cleverly puncturing an attempt of Polish Esperantists to try to “present Esperanto’s creator as a Pole, rather than a Russian, because he lived for many years in Warsaw.”¹¹ Roberto Garvía, calls Białystok “a multi ethnic, but predominantly Jewish town”¹², and depicts Zamenhof mainly as the citizen of the Russian Empire, almost entirely skipping his Polish connection. Nor does he ever mention the Polish Esperanto Movement. Esther Shor mostly focuses on the cosmopolitanism of the Esperanto creator, and sadly, Polish Esperantists are not given any

⁷ Norman Davies, *God’s Playground. A History of Poland* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1981), p. 404.

⁸ Ibid, p. 405.

⁹ Esther Shor, *Bridge of Words* (New York: Metropolitan Books Henry Holt and Company, 2016), p. 101.

¹⁰ Alexander Korzhenkov, *Zamenhof. The Life, Works and Ideas of the Author of Esperanto* (New York: Mondial, 2009), p. 3.

¹¹ Ibid, p. 5.

¹² Roberto Garvía, *Esperanto and Its Rivals. The Struggle for and International Language* (Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 2015), p. 60.

insight by her, either. Finally, in his *Dangerous Language – Esperanto under Hitler and Stalin*, Ulrich Lins does mention Poland yet only in the context of persecution of the Esperanto movement.

There also exists a substantial number of biographical works on Ludwik Zamenhof and his family members.¹³ These works, however, though detailed, explore mostly the personal side of the founder of the movement, present him, together with his family, in a widely international context, focusing on his Jewish influences, the multicultural context he and his family were raised in, his calling, vision and passion. Rarely do they go deeper into the Polish context or analyse the popularity and spread of the movement in Poland.

Yet, after enough research, it becomes obvious that there was a time during which Esperanto in Poland flourished and even became fashionable. Although the aforementioned sources' focus does not fully integrate the Polish scene, it would be pointless, though to completely reject them, as they offer a valuable insight into different contexts and different perspectives on the topic and will help me balance my take on the Polish Esperanto Movement in the early 20th century. As Garvía, Schor and Lins extensively focus on the internationalism of Esperanto as represented by organisations such as SAT (Sennacieca Asocio Tutmonda or World Anational Organisation), I will be trying to contrast their content with the Polish situation, where the presence of SAT was minimal and the concept of statelessness mostly rejected. In this thesis, I will

¹³ The titles worth mentioning here are *Vivo de Zamenhof* (London: Brita Esperanto Asocio, 1920) by Edmond Privat, *Zamenhof: The Life, Works and Ideas of the Author of Esperanto* (New York: Mondial, 2009) by Alexander Korzhenkov, *Lidia: The life of Lidia Zamenhof, daughter of Esperanto* (Oxford: George Ronald, 1985) by Wendy Heller, *Ludwik Zamenhof* (Kraków: Nomos, 2012) by Walter Żelazny, *Ludwik Zamenhof wobec kwestii żydowskiej* (Kraków, Budapest: Austeria, 2012) by Agnieszka Jagodzińska, as well as the works of Roman Dobrzyński, such as *Ulica Zamenhofa* (Bielsko-Biała: KLEKS, 2003), which features an interview with Zamenhof's grandson, and, the most recent publication, *Zamenhof in Warsaw* (Białystok: Białystok Cultural Centre, 2019), which sheds a closer light on the city in which Zamenhof spent most of his life.

demonstrate how Polish Esperantists still managed to successfully build transnational connections and, at the same time, use it to promote their nation.

1.3 Primary sources

The primary sources for this research mostly come from Polish national archives in Warsaw, Kraków and Łódź. They include contemporary newspapers, magazines, police records, ministerial documents, notes and correspondence from various embassies, schools, and associations, as well as travel brochures, Esperanto associations' and official congress records and promotional materials. Another major source I will make use of is *Pola Esperantisto* (PE), a bi-monthly newspaper published by the Polish Esperanto Association between 1906 and 1937, which can be found in its digital form in the archives of the Austrian National Library. In addition, I shall examine contemporary newspapers and magazines from across political spectrum of the time available digitally from Jagiellońska Biblioteka Cyfrowa and other online libraries. I will also use personal chronicles, letters and memos of recognised individual Esperantists, such as Odo Bujwid, Emilian Loth and Henryk Pfeiffer, firstly, as their collections offer a thorough insight into the Esperanto movement in the early 20th century Poland, and secondly because I see them as representative of a certain persona which, in my view, personifies a “typical” Polish Esperantist of the time.

1.4 Structure

This thesis is divided into four major chapters. The first chapter, *Who were the Esperantists?*, I shall mainly discuss the socioeconomic background of Esperantists in pre-WW2 Poland. I will argue that Esperanto, even though designed with the best of intentions to connect humanity and break interpersonal barriers between people, in Poland was, in fact, chiefly driven, proselytized, and utilised by the professional middle classes, artists and broadly understood intelligentsia, or, as we would say it these days, “the liberal elites”. I will explain how the idea of Polishness permeated the core of the Esperanto movement in Poland. I will also try to give justice to the working-class Esperanto association and analyse various ways in which the idea of an easy-to-learn *lingvo internacia* appealed to the working-class Polish proletariat.

The second chapter, *Esperanto as a means of furthering the Polish cause* will focus on how Esperanto served as a tool of communication on the international stage with a clear aim of furthering “the Polish cause” before 1918, and later to advertise the reborn state. I will show how Esperanto was used to reach out to the international audiences to validate and consolidate the influence of Poland and its positive image abroad. Here, a variety of travel brochures, embassy correspondence and personal letters will be analysed, as well as Esperanto journals and materials promoting World Esperanto Congresses, especially the two key ones which will serve as focal points for my research: Kraków 1912 and Warsaw 1937.

In the third and final chapter, *The critical voices*, I shall present a vast array of not always positive views towards the Esperanto movement in Poland. In this chapter I will try to analyse the popular opinion of Esperanto in Poland and various attitudes towards the whole concept of an international language and the role it was meant to serve at the time. I will analyse how, at various times, the idea of Esperanto clashed with the concept of Polishness, and why it was often seen as

a threat to Polish nationalism. I will focus on and present the criticism of all sorts that Esperanto and Esperantists had to face at the time. I will also ask questions whether these critical voices contributed towards Esperanto slowly losing its clout and public appeal. In this part of my thesis, I shall devote more attention to different Esperanto sub-groups and expose their different treatment by the Polish authorities. I will primarily base my research on various media, literary critiques, as well as the police files and governmental decisions which would often make or break an existing or aspiring Esperanto association. The difference in status between different Esperanto associations was most clearly evident after the Polish-Soviet war of 1919-1920, when the guards were kept very high in terms of detecting potential communists and enemies of state. Since around the same time, Esperanto has also become a tool of Marxist propaganda in Bolshevik Russia, and its certain branches were deemed highly suspicious across Europe. I will therefore try to depict the unique situation in Poland and the hurdles that had to be overcome in order to start and continue running an Esperanto movement and the level of scrutiny Esperanto groups were exposed to.

CHAPTER 1

Who were the Esperantists?

2.1 Introduction

When Zamenhof published his *Unua Libro* in 1887, he chose Russian as the language of the publication. It is claimed that doing so was the safest option, as the tsarist powers-that-be would not raise any suspicions: a publication in Polish, on the other hand, may have been riskier given the political climate and censorship efforts of Russification since later 19th century. More importantly, however, the language was presented to the censors as “benign nonsense”¹⁴ Indeed, the book, and the later the movement were initially looked upon with a great degree of permissiveness and indulgence, a sort of “harmless lunatic” thing. It was only later, when the movement consolidated itself and became more powerful, influential, or even radical turn among some circles, that it started to be seen as a “dangerous language”.

The question then remains: how has Esperanto managed to gain such significance and recognition in a relatively short period of time? Of course, it was the brilliant idea and campaign of Zamenhof, who collected pledges from his first readers. By doing so, he subsequently discovered a niche, a vacuum in the society, which he then filled with Esperanto. The movement would not have set off, had it not been for those who positively responded to Zamenhof’s call and passed it on to others. It is all the more pronounced in Poland, where the movement received very little if any financial backing from the authorities: neither during the partition time, nor as a reborn nation. Quite understandably, the new country after 1918 had other, more urgent expenses, and so the whole Esperanto initiative in Poland was almost entirely at the mercy of its devoted members,

¹⁴ Ulrich Lins, *Dangerous Language: Esperanto under Hitler and Stalin* (Bonn: Palgrave Macmillan, 2016), p.11.

enthusiasts, activists and well-wishers. In this chapter, I shall analyse the Esperanto movement and its socio-political components and try to identify these unfulfilled needs which urged early Esperantists to invest their time, energy and resources into this brand new, untested and vaguely suspicious movement.

2.2 Modernists and modernisers

The very first article in the very first publication of *Pola Esperantisto* (*The Polish Esperantist*), the official periodical of the Polish Esperantists, was notably written by Edmund Libański (1862-1928), an engineer (and so much more!) from Lviv.¹⁵ Indeed, looking at Libański's colourful life and a wide palette of interest, one cannot help but imagine a man of inexhaustible energy, passion and ideas, a true man of renaissance. Apart from being an engineer, Libański was an aviator, constructor, map maker, author, editor, translator, a cinema enthusiast, photographer, and a worshipper of general technological progress.¹⁶ Not afraid to face challenges, and clearly with a passion to conquer new peaks – both literally and metaphorically - Libański was fascinated by Everest climbing, just as he was by, spiritualism¹⁷. Most notably, however, he held socialist

¹⁵ Edmund Libański, „Ni laboru kaj esperu!”, PE: July 1906, p.1.

¹⁶ Agnieszka J. Cieślikowska, „Edmund Libański i jego lwowskie czasopismo 'Przemysłowiec' [The Industrialist] (1903–1910)” *Rocznik Historii Prasy Polskiej* Tom XIX, Zeszyt 3, 2016.

¹⁷ In 1922, Libański published a book on the history of spiritualism in Poland, *Tajemnice Badań Spirytystycznych w Świetle Badań Naukowych*, which testifies his curiosity and appetite for knowledge knew no bounds. It is worth pointing out that spiritism was arguably a respectable “science” in modernism, differentiating it from magic as such, see: Leigh Wilson, *Modernism and Magic – experiments with spiritualism, theosophy and the occult*. (Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2013).

views and pioneered as a social education on a mission to illuminate the masses by his contribution to the People's University in Kraków (Towarzystwo Uniwersytetu Ludowego im A. Mickiewicza (TUL)), where he keenly delivered lectures and on the latest trends and developments in the world.¹⁸ It is indeed little wonder that a man of his energy and vision would become one of the first in his homeland to enthusiastically sail the uncharted waters of Esperanto.

In his opening address to the would-be readers of *Pola Esperantisto*, titled “Let’s work and hope”, Libański explicitly references

the flower of global intelligentsia: scientists, professors, politicians, writers, philosophers, publicists, distinguished engineers, industrialists, leaders of academia and other reputable institutions¹⁹

As the main users of Esperanto, the language which he depicts in a truly triumphalist and prophetic manner, comparing its invention to that of Stephenson’s steam engine. Reading about the inexhaustible achievements and interests of Edmund Libański, one can see clearly why a man like him should become attracted by the new language: it would encourage international cooperation, enhance civilization and promote science and technology to the general public in a clear and simple manner. To people like Libański, Esperanto was nothing but yet another ingenious modern invention, a fruit of an enlightened mind generously gifted to the masses. Subsequently, in his

¹⁸Barbara Gierszewska, ”Inżynier Edmund Libański: popularyzator nauki i techniki we Lwowie w początkach XX wieku,” *Kwartalnik Historii Nauki i Techniki* 49/2, 2004, ps 53-68.

¹⁹ Edmind Libański, ”Ni laboru kaj esperu!”, PE: July 1906, p. 2.

Lvivian paper, *Przemysłowiec*, published between 1903 and 1911 with the idea of promoting technological advancement and local industry as the means of the economic revival of the country, Libański dedicated a column to the language.

Looking through the materials available on the early Polish Esperantists, one quickly notices that the energetic persona of Libański together with his endless curiosity was a common trait amongst many. He and people like him, with their inexhaustible energy and a strong will to reform things were the engine that pushed the Esperanto movement forward. They clearly had various interests and high hopes for a better future for humankind.

Libański was not wrong in identifying his audience. Starting with the creator of the language, Ludwik Lazar Zamenhof, a well-educated professional ophthalmologist from a liberal Jewish family, all the way through to his best Polish accomplice, Antoni Grabowski, a chemist, publicist, translator, and poet, who famously translated the great Polish national epic, “Pan Tadeusz” into Esperanto²⁰, and ending with pretty much every name in Józef Golec’s “Słownik Esperantystów Polskich” (A Dictionary of Polish Esperantists) one observes a similar trend. Nearly each and every person associated with the early Esperanto movement belonged to what we would call by today’s terms, “the liberal elites”. This was not much different from the global profile of a typical Esperantist. As Garvía notes in his book “Esperanto and its Rivals: the Struggle for an International Language”, an average Esperantist was much better educated than the general population in their country of origin and often had a university degree.²¹ It is, nonetheless, a crucial feature which must be stated in order to get a full grasp of the Esperanto movement in Poland.

²⁰ Józef Golec, *Słownik Biograficzny Esperantystów Polskich* (Cieszyn: Oficyna Joseph Golec, 2010), p. 64.

²¹ Garvia, *Esperanto...*, p. 97.

The profession was by itself a primary class marker. The early Polish esperantists were mostly teachers, professors, engineers, pedagogues, linguists, lawyers, doctors, artists. A notable example is Dr Odo Bujwid, the leader of the Kraków Esperantists, a renowned Polish bacteriologist, and his wife, Kazimiera, one of the first Polish “liberal feminists” advocating women’s rights, promoting girls’ education and their full social participation. Kazimierz Bein, aka. Kabe, the renowned creator of the first Esperanto dictionary, left the movement in 1911 to dedicate himself fully to his initial calling, medicine, contributing a new word to Esperanto in the process - kabei, meaning “to leave abruptly”²²

The same middle-class character is also true for the socialists among the esperantists. Leopold Kronenberg was a teacher, a librarian and a city councilor. Even Jan Zawada, perhaps the most leftist Esperantist of the time and an active member of the Polish labour Esperanto association “Praca -Laboro” which he joined early on from its inception in 1919²³, only worked in the coal mine “for a short time”²⁴, after which he conveniently decided to become a trade union activist and publicist, travelling extensively across Europe and later finding his calling in teaching German.

Interestingly, most of these people were not trained linguists. Quite the opposite, as it was in the case of Zamenhof himself, their primary professional interests lay in sciences. This, however, did not limit them in the slightest, and they proved their worth as “talented amateurs” by pursuing their more liberal interests. The pioneers of Esperanto in Poland were certainly well-rounded, accomplished, dedicated people with a wide array of hobbies to enjoy, causes to support and memberships to hold. They indeed personified the very spirit of Modernism, an era

²² Reta Vortaro <<http://www.reta-vortaro.de/revo/art/kabe.html>>.

²³ PE: 1975, 5/6 (Septembro-December) “Jan Zawada Obituary”, p. 8.

²⁴ Golec, *Słownik...*, p. 266.

characterised by its extensive focus on progress, utilitarianism, individualism, breaking away from tradition and improving human existence through innovation: they attended popular international exhibitions, followed the latest technological trends and did their best to popularise their use. Let us look at another example, Emilian Loth.

Emilian Loth (1888-1973) was an Esperantist, a scientist, and a chemical engineer from Pabianice near Łódź, but first and foremost, a reputable member of the city's establishment. Among the rich collection of his speeches, letters and reports found at the Łódź National Archives²⁵, there are several reports from the automobile exhibitions (in Berlin and Italy) a commencement speech at the Łódź Exhibition of Inventions in 1939, an award-giving speech to a member of the Łódź Technical Association (in his capacity of the association manager), as well as correspondence from his Rotary Club activity. All these contributions point to a well-travelled citizen of the world, a European in the truest sense of the word, as well as a community leader, practicing what he preaches. Again, Loth's Esperanto engagement is not accidental – it is just a missing puzzle to complete the full picture of a liberal inventor, a global, progressive thinker, but a local player, set on improving the life of his compatriots.

In conclusion, the popularity of Esperanto in Poland was in tune with the *Zeitgeist* of early 20th century Europe. The chief motivation for many Poles to use and promote Esperanto stemmed from general curiosity, the desire to keep up with the times, to improve their communities, modernize the country and to contribute on a social level. These motifs were not entirely altruistic and selfless: in the process, people like Loth, Bujwid and his spouse, or Libański would gain even

²⁵ Archiwum Dr Emiliana Lotha Inżyniera Chemika w Pabianicach. Przemówienia na uroczystościach, zebraniach, odczytach, notatki z podróży zagranicznych. 1914-1939. Sygnatura 8.

more recognition, represent their communities on the local and international stage, as well as improve their own skills and gain social clout.

2.3 Bourgeoisie of the world, unite!

It undoubtedly required a lot of time to successfully cultivate so many activities and passions. This is yet another factor proving the fundamentally middle-class origin of the early Esperantists: the very fact they could afford to dedicate their time to the vast array of hobbies, among which Esperanto was just a frivolous addition. Even though many authors rightly observe the liberal demographics of the early Esperantists, they often tend to depict them as some sort of daydreamers, pacifists learning Esperanto to achieve a greater cause of united mankind. Yet, when it comes to the Polish Esperanto Society in its early days, one gets the impression its primary role was entertainment. The membership of the club offered a rather high social value to its participants, playing the role of “networking events”, rather than being strictly language oriented.

Reading the volumes of *Pola Esperantisto*, one cannot help wishing they could travel back in time: the pages are full of socially alluring events and activities. The subscribers to the March 1911 issue received an invitation to a ball hosted by the Academic Esperanto Association in Kraków under the patronage of the contemporary civic elites of the city: the University rector, the city mayor, and Odo Bujwid, the head of the Kraków Esperanto Association.²⁶ Other social activities included Esperanto choirs, poetry recitals and drama clubs aimed at making the

²⁶ PE: March 1911, p. 43.

movement more varied and appealing.²⁷ As we can read in the April/May issue of 1910 *Pola Esperantisto*, even a special Entertainment Committee (*Komisja Zabaw*) was established to embellish the social programs.²⁸ The magazine's volumes featured song books with notes – clearly for those able to play the piano, poetry, and multiple translations of fine literature to enrich the spirit. On top of that, there were regular congresses frequented by the Esperanto crowd. They certainly were grand occasions to mix and mingle with the finest minds and keenest spirits of the early twentieth-century Europe. They usually featured a diverse cultural program, which included sightseeing of the host city, trips, various presentations, dinners, balls, club meetings pandering to every interest or political persuasion, speeches, lectures and general addresses, religious services, art programs including theatre and music performances. In a country where, according to Norman Davies, 92 % of the population were peasants and manual workers²⁹, it is fair to conclude that it was only the narrow minority of city-dwelling intelligentsia and entrepreneurs who could allow themselves to indulge in this sort of entertainment.

As Kraków was preparing to host the 1912 International Congress, an article in the April issue of *Pola Esperantisto* remarks,

(...) 2000 foreigners representing several different nationalities will take part in the Congress. As the Esperanto Movement is popular mostly among the educated class, these visitors form the social elites of their societies.³⁰

²⁷ PE: October 1922, p.13.

²⁸ PE: April/May 1910, p.57.

²⁹ Davies, *God's Playground*, p. 410.

³⁰ PE: April 1912, p. 58.

The Polish Esperantists were clearly excited by the prospect of mixing with the global elites and it was them they were looking forward to hosting and showing around. Although the article later goes on to talk about brotherhood “in the nationalistic madness of our times”³¹, it is obvious that this brotherhood lies along the class lines.

The first volumes of *Pola Esperantisto* cater to many other hobbies and needs of their readers through its numerous adverts. The issues of 1908 *Pola Esperantisto* openly target petit bourgeoisie by feature advertisements of lingerie and duvets, wedding and newborn layettes, pianos and piano fortes. They did not forget about industrialists, business and property owners by placing advertisements of HR agencies which provided agricultural and factory workers (“up to 500 a year”),³² as well as clerical help with invoices and typing. Lawyers would offer their assistance with buying, selling, leasing, and renting property. *Rolnik i hodowca*, a magazine for the landed gentry was hoping to attract the readership of *Pola Esperantisto*.³³ Massage and “Swedish gymnastics” parlours would offer their services to those craving some physical activity; a reader of 1908 -1909 *Pola Esperantisto* would have no problems finding best furniture shops, babysitting agencies, or choosing the right perfume. The finest goods were offered to the sophisticated audience, clearly believed to be able to afford them.

It is little wonder that Esperanto found its supporter among the Polish artistic elite. A fine example here is Zofia Batycka (1907-1989), a Lvivian actress from a wealthy, reputable family

³¹ Ibid.

³² PE: 1908 (advertisement section).

³³ PE: 1909 (advertisement section).

and 1930 Miss Polonia, at some point engaged to the world-renowned Polish tenor, Jan Kiepura.³⁴ Batycka was fluent in four languages including Esperanto and actively attended International Congresses, including the 1932 International Esperanto Congress in Paris³⁵ and the 1931 Kraków Congress, during which she gained universal approval wearing a traditional Cracovian dress to the ball.³⁶ Yet, it is doubtful that her motivation to learn Esperanto originated in a desire to promote world peace or any other cause greater than launching her own international acting career.

Batycka was not an exception in her knowledge of foreign languages at the time. It was indeed expected of a well-brought up young man or woman to achieve a certain level of fluency in both modern and ancient languages. Therefore, Esperanto found a fertile ground to comfortably settle in the nice, liberal private schools of Kraków, Lviv and Warsaw, where the golden boys and girls received their expensive education. For high-profile, renowned institutions, like the Private Liceum and Gimnazjum for Girls named after Helena Kaplińska, where girls keenly corresponded with their Swedish counterparts in broken Esperanto³⁷, adding a new-fangled subject certainly raised their profile and attracted more fashionable Cracovian parents together with their fees.

As opposed to what mainstream authors, such as Esther Schor and Roberto Garvía are trying to suggest, Esperanto in Poland was very often far removed from the urge to unite mankind

³⁴ Gregory Shamborovsky (translated by Areta Kovalska), “Zofia Batycka: The Lvivian Who Became Miss Polonia and a Famous Film Actress,” *Forgotten Galicia*. 3 July 2018.

<<https://forgottengalicia.com/zofia-batycka-lvivian-became-miss-polonia-and-famous-film-actress>>.

³⁵ Narodowe Archiwum Cyfrowe: Image: *Zofia Batycka*, 1932, Sygnatura 1-K-7448

<<https://audiovis.nac.gov.pl/obraz/73847/>>.

³⁶ “Gwiazdy i gwiazdory filmu polskiego,” *Pomocniczy Język Światowy*, nr 8-9 (Kraków: August-September 1931), p. 2.

³⁷ Archiwum Narodowe w Karkowie: Korespondencja uczennic szkoły z młodzieżą z miasta Växjö (w języku esperanto). Sygnatura LGK 207.

and was more often than not a way to pass the time, a fashionable trend embraced by celebrities of the time, and a golden opportunity to “network” with other Polish and European professionals, thus advancing one’s career or social status.

It must be noted, despite all which has been stated above, that the Esperanto movement did have supporters among Poland’s working classes. In the post-1918 independent and democratic Poland, saw the formation of the first Polish political parties and the urban workers in particular began to see their common predicament.³⁸ They saw an opportunity in Esperanto. The language’s universal nature and socialism were in many cases a natural fit: the mass appeal of *lingvo internacia*, the nurture-over-nature element, internationalism, progressivism, statelessness and the lack of apparent roots spoke to the minds and hearts of the Left. In independent Poland after 1918, the socialists ran their own Esperanto club “Laboro-Praca” under the leadership of Jan Zawada.³⁹ The Polish Socialist Party’s newspaper “Robotnik” had a regular “Esperanto Corner” bringing the news from the world of Esperanto to its working-class readership. It was also spoke highly of in many volumes of “Gazeta Robotnicza” the Silesian PPS paper, as well as a more radical publication, “Łodzianin”.

The Left saw Esperanto as a tool of modernization, indispensable in the fast-moving world. It was an easy tool of communication between nations, in tune with the Marxist motto, “Workers of the world, unite!”. In “Robotnik”, on many occasions, Esperanto is being praised as the language of progress, technology and world peace. As the author of the Esperanto Corner in “Robotnik” (October 1927) notes, not a single distinguished socialist figure held hostile view towards

³⁸ There is little evidence for the movement finding any supporters under thatched roofs of villagers, while it was heavily promoted in cities and towns.

³⁹ ”Pierwszy Wszechpolski Kongres Esperantystów”, *Robotnik*, nr 151, Warsaw: 6 June 1922.

Esperanto. He later goes on to quote Romaine Roland, a lifelong Stalin admirer and the promoter of the so-called “people’s theatre” who speaks of Zamenhof as the one who sensed a “great need” among the people of the world, a visionary and, indeed, a liberator of the masses.⁴⁰

Esperanto was praised for its utilitarianism and was depicted as a “foreign” language which was particularly easy to learn for a typical labourer after a day’s of hard work and indeed could be mastered in 3 months-time.⁴¹ Despite, or perhaps due to the lack of means and qualified teachers, a lot learning would take place by correspondence.⁴² Because of the unstable economic situation in the reborn country, many workers were desperately trying to learn a language which, in a relatively short time, could considerably improve their earning prospects, or even offer a new chance abroad. As a result, Esperanto was the most popular foreign language of choice to be studied at Warsaw’s People University and its number of learners was “considerably larger than those taking English”⁴³

TUR – Towarzystwo Uniwersytetu Robotniczego, a socialist educational institution, would also offer free courses to working-class Esperanto learners⁴⁴ and although some socialist critics of Esperanto would view it an unnecessary luxury or even as another new evil device of the

⁴⁰ “Kącik Esperancki”, *Robotnik*, nr 299, Warsaw: 31 October 1927.

⁴¹ “Czy warto uczyć się esperanta?”, *Silacz. Dodatek do nr. 7 „Gazety Robotniczej”*, 10 January 1926.

⁴² *Łodzianin*, Nr 37(362) (Łódź: 10 September 1922), p.7.

⁴³ “Esperanto”, *The Review of Reviews* ed. William Thomas Stead, Vol. 39, London: January-June 1909, p. 194.

⁴⁴ Andrzej Maria Gajzler “Organizacja Młodzieży Towarzystwa Uniwersytetu Robotniczego 1923—1936,” *Prace Monograficzne nr 162* (Kraków: Wydawnictwo Naukowe WSP, 1993), pp 72-73, 78.

bourgeoisie desiring to unite in world-dominance⁴⁵, in the country where one person in five could not read and write⁴⁶, Esperanto was primarily seen as a tool to fight illiteracy.

The idea of “memeduko per Esperanto”, or self-learning through Esperanto, was particularly strong among the working-class circles, who lost their trust in any official channels.

In our young country, there’s a lot of work to be done to educate the proletariat, and even more to root out illiteracy. The bourgeois circles will not do it, on the contrary, they would want to maintain the present state of darkness in perpetuity.⁴⁷

The anonymous author of the article where the above fragment comes from goes on to promote Esperanto as a language that would not only offer the workers a precious means of communication, but, above all, open their eyes to the world and make them realise the inferiority of their position in Poland, in contrast to the proletarians in other “civilised” lands.

We must show the new proletarian generation the cultures of foreign countries, let them come closer to the comrades of the world, let them feel they rank lower than the civilised proletarians. Let them share their joy of fighting for better

⁴⁵ *Silacz*.

⁴⁶ Piotr Sewruk, ”Jedyny taki uniwersytet w Lublinie. Słuchacze głównie ze środowiska proletariackiego, ponad połowa bezrobotna”, *Gazeta Wyborcza* (Lublin, 30 March 2018).

⁴⁷ *Silacz*: W młodem naszym państwie...

social rights, let them find brothers-in-arms among the Swedes, Germans, Japanese, Brits or the awakening Chinese.⁴⁸

As we notice in this fragment, Esperanto could take a very militant turn and was being clearly used to incite social divisions and class struggles. It did, quite rightly underscore the desperate position of the Polish workers of the time, who did not always enjoy the same reforms and rights as workers from other, more established and richer countries. It was “a fight against national, religious or linguistic superstitions - for a new culture – socialism.”⁴⁹ At the same time, its tone seems only one step away from SAT (Sennacieca Asocio Tutmonda), the infamous communist wing of Esperanto.

In the aftermath of the Polish-Soviet war of 1918-1920, this organisation was under particular scrutiny from the police, and, according to the Krakow Police archives, did not start a formal organisation on the Polish soil, despite having a few individual members in existence, as well as a handful of *Sanatiulo*, a radical-left wing publication, colporteurs.⁵⁰ In 1925, *Łodzianin*, a left-wing weekly publication reported on the SAT congress taking place in Vienna. Although the congress had no Polish delegates, the paper happily reports on how “pleasant” it was to see socialists, communists, anarchists, syndicalists, athletes, teetotallers (sic!), free thinkers and scouts speaking one language and working together to introduce Esperanto to their organisations.⁵¹ In

⁴⁸ Ibid: Trzeba młodemu pokoleniu proletarjackiemu...

⁴⁹ ”IV wszechpolski kongres esperantystów w Łodzi”, *Łodzianin*, nr 40 (Łódź: 27 September 1930) p. 5.

⁵⁰ Archiwum Narodowe w Krakowie. Starostwo Grodzkie Krakowskie. *Komenda Policji Pństwowej m. Krakowa*. Sygnatura 724.

⁵¹ ”V Kongres robotniczej międzynarodówki esperanckiej”, *Łodzianin*, nr 34 (Łódź: 22 August 1925) p. 2.

1938, a student, Janina Misiewiczówna, the leader of the Independent Socialist Youth Club, was arrested in Vilnius for putting up a poster featuring four images: the first one depicted a crucified, bloodied labourer with a Polish general, a priest and a capitalist standing by, the second showed a tax collector taking away the last cow from a peasant, in the third picture one could see a dollar note superimposed on the globe, and the fourth depicted political prisoners asking for their release - in Esperanto.⁵² Despite these minor incidents, however, the communist or any radical left-wing Esperanto voices in Poland stood no chance against the authorities and would be promptly squashed.

Speaking of the class-based distribution of Esperanto, one quickly observes, that just as there were not too many activists or learners among peasants, the interest in Esperanto among the Polish aristocracy was clearly lacking. The June 1911 issue of *Pola Esperantisto* offers a first-page translation of a French article by Ernest Archdeacken, who shames the aristocrats and the rich for their lack of support for the movement, calling them out for being nothing but dim-witted passive users of technological inventions: “Those who ridiculed it yesterday, today are splashing mud speeding in their cars.”⁵³ He regrets that once again it is the “materially impaired circles”⁵⁴ who truly understand the significance of the new language. In France, the article might have caused a response: a year later, in January 1912, *Pola Esperantisto* reports on an official dinner of the Paris Esperanto Association attended by a senator, an archbishop and a count, during which Mr Michelin offered a 20 000-franc scholarship to support French schoolchildren learning Esperanto. Sadly, although many businesses and industrialists clearly appreciated the benefits of a common language

⁵² “Socjalizm ośmiesz religię katoliczą i szerzy komunizm”, *Robotnik Katolicki*, nr 6 (Tarnów: 1 November 1938), p. 5.

⁵³ PE: June 1911.

⁵⁴ Ibid.

and advocated the teaching of Esperanto in trade schools⁵⁵, such generous gifts were not offered from any Polish upper-class echelons of the time, and so it was left to the “materially impaired circles” to promote the movement with their modest means. The Polish Esperanto movement was definitely not rich: throughout the whole historical period presented in this thesis, the Esperantists suffer countless financial shortages, and send out desperate pleas for support to the authorities, asking for money or at least classrooms to continue their activities⁵⁶ most likely achieving nothing more than a public transport discount.⁵⁷ As Stanisław Dobrzański reports in the June/July 1910 issue of *Pola Esperantisto*, several participants attending the congress in Boulogne-sur-Mer in 1906 could not afford 8 francs to attend a festivity.⁵⁸

2.4 Patriots and misfits

Impoverished as some of the early Polished Esperantists may have been, the core of the movement was elite, which, at the time, was about more than money and class. It was first and foremost a matter of identity. To understand what it meant to belong to the Polish elite of the time, one has to understand its history. Starting with the freedoms granted to its vast number of nobles and guaranteed by Pacta Conventa and Henrician Articles, who, as opposed to the neighbouring absolute monarchies, were able to elect their king, all the way to the 3rd of May Constitution,

⁵⁵ PE: April 1910.

⁵⁶ Archiwum Państwowe w Łodzi. *Pisma przychodzące do Sekcji Szkolnej – prośby o pomoc finansową instytucji i stowarzyszeń oświatowych na cele oświaty, kursy biblioteczne i esperanto*. Sygnatura 182/136. 1916.

⁵⁷ Archiwum Akt Nowych w Warszawie. *Poselstwo RP w Wiedniu. List w sprawie światowego zjazdu esperantystów*. 3 January 1935. Sygnatura 2975.

⁵⁸ “Esperanto u nas”, PE: June-July 1910, p. 70.

liberalizing and reforming the country, and unprecedented in Europe, Poland took great pride in its democratic foundations. Yet, despite these early attempts, Poland had not achieved true democracy and social equality for a long time. The democracy was in fact an oligarchy, and belonged to the narrow few, who were noble, mostly educated and politically informed. Throughout the ages, it was in the hands of this narrow, Catholic, Polish-speaking gentry to carry the burden and, indeed, the very idea of Polishness on their shoulders.⁵⁹ Meanwhile, the vast majority had no greater sense of national belonging. Therefore, it has always been a privilege and a sacred duty of the elites to educate the masses. This superior attitude is clearly noticeable among the Polish Esperantists. In the June/July 1910 issue, *Pola Esperantisto* talks about equality and removing the shackles of serfdom. “It is our patriotic duty” to promote Esperanto. Yet, it is doubtful he means actual serfs: he is instead making a veiled reference to the occupiers, not sparing much thought to the oppressed peasants of the land.

Esperanto in Poland is, on many occasions, presented as the language of progress, but also as an educational and civilizational mission, in tune with the idea of “*praca organiczna*”, organic work, promoted by the Polish elites as a means of rebuilding and reforming the country bottom-up. The nation is but one living organism and therefore all its parts were to be engaged in the national revival. The attitude of the “head” to the remaining body parts was, however, superior and patronizing. In an article titled “The Duty of an Esperantist” from August 1910, the author mentions the low level of intellectual development among the masses⁶⁰ thus placing his readership

⁵⁹ Ilya Prizel, *National Identity and Foreign Policy: Nationalism and Leadership in Poland, Russia and Ukraine* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1998) p. 38.

⁶⁰ “Obowiązek Esperantysty” PE: August 1910, p. 103.

on a higher pedestal than other. The duty of an Esperantist was therefore to use Esperanto to raise the general intellectual as well as material levels among the unenlightened masses.

Despite all the lofty slogans and certainly much effort, there is little evidence that the Esperantists managed to achieve their goal. Esperanto courses were usually private and took place in cities and bigger towns. Even though Esperanto was introduced, and indeed enjoyed great popularity in People's and Workers' Universities, it never really succeeded in making its way into general education. In the country where a fifth of the citizens could not read or write, a success on this scale was simply unfeasible.

Esther Schor, the author of "Bridge of Words" offers a very thorough, but not entirely proportionate, at least in the Polish case, classification of the initial Esperantists.⁶¹ She devotes a whole chapter to Eugene Adam ("Lanti") the founder of the national, socialist Esperanto movement SAT and contrasts it with the universalism of Lidia Zamenhof, as if universalism was the mainstream feature of the global Esperanto movement of the time. This certainly was not the case in Poland, where cosmopolitanism was seen as a vice rather than a virtue.

We know cosmopolitans – people whose homelands are where it is most convenient, egoists dressed in grand words, who dodge their first responsibility by hiding behind the last. We know chauvinists, in front of their doghouse, on a chain, growling at the whole world. We also know human oxen, whose mouths always

⁶¹ Schor, *Bridge...*, p.142.

work for their stomachs; whose task is to be herded where they belong. Among them, the idea of mankind got lost.⁶²

As we can observe from the above fragment, cosmopolitanism was not an important value for the early Polish Esperantists. They saw its faults and despised it as much as they despised chauvinism. In the 1909 article titled “The love of Fatherland and Esperantism”, R. Maske, while writing a diatribe against nationalism, at the same time manages to call cosmopolitanism “contrary to human nature”⁶³. This did not change after 1918. In 1923, Polish Esperantists signed the “Poznań Declaration” in which they recognized Esperanto as a means of representing Poland abroad and declared to use exclusively Polish to communicate with people and institutions on Polish territory.⁶⁴ They made it clear that they shall do their best to combat the use of Esperanto for “cosmopolitan agitation”⁶⁵ The later issues of *Pola Esperantisto* highlight this by referring to both the Boulogne Declaration and the Poznań Declaration of the cover page.

In 1921, the daughter of Ludwik Zamenhof, Lidia Zamenhof, together with her other family members, started a new Esperanto Club named “Konkordo”.⁶⁶ The creation of the club could have been a response to the anti-Semitic persecutions Lidia witnessed as a student at a Polish university.⁶⁷ The new club was designed to promote the ideas of Homoranism, which was the belief in the unity of human mankind, very much in tune with Lidia’s religious beliefs. As a member of

⁶² “Vox in Dezerto”, PE: December 1908, p. 186.

⁶³ R. Maske, “Miłość Ojczyzny a Esperantyzm” PE: July – August 1909, p. 120.

⁶⁴ PE: May-June, pp. 110-111.

⁶⁵ Ibid p.111.

⁶⁶ Schor, *Bridge...*, p. 182

⁶⁷ Wendy Heller, *Lidia: The Life of Lidia Zamenhof Daughter of Esperanto* (Oxford: George Ronald, 1985), p.60.

the Baha'i community, Lidia had a deep belief in a stateless world where everyone was equal. This, however, was the final straw for the Polish Esperanto Society, which in the 1924 Jan-Feb issue of *Pola Esperantisto* published an official statement, officially distancing itself from both the socialist "Laboro" and the cosmopolitan "Konkordo" clubs, dubbing itself the official, "patriotic" Esperanto Association.⁶⁸ It also changed its name in Esperanto from "Societo" to "Asocio", most likely to distance itself even further from any notion or suspicion of socialism.⁶⁹

Through its actions, the Polish Esperanto Society was sending a very strong signal to any minority members: assimilate or get out. At the same time, however, Esperanto offered those who did not quite fit the "true Pole" label, an opportunity to blend in. The key players on the mainstream Polish Esperanto stage included Polonised, fully assimilated Jews, who on many occasions declared their undying bond with the nation. A prime example here is Julian Tuwim, who famously said, "My homeland is the Polish language" and whose love for Polish is "too off-putting" for many Jews until today.⁷⁰ Another prominent Jewish figure of the mainstream Esperanto movement in Poland is Leo Belmont (Leopold Blumental) who would try to claim Zamenhof's Polishness by inventing patriotic rhymes in which Zamenhof would declare his Polishness.⁷¹ Both of these writers would translate volumes of Polish literature into Esperanto and the movement owes a lot to their countless contributions and engagement⁷². In Łódź, the most famous Esperanto activists

⁶⁸ PE: Jan – Feb 1924, p. 2.

⁶⁹ Ibid.

⁷⁰ Myer Siemiatycki, "Why Is the Great Poet Tuwim Beloved by Poles, Yet Forgotten by Jews?" *The Jerusalem Post* | *JPost.com*, 24 Dec. 2019.

⁷¹ Walter Żelazny, "Ludwik Zamenhof – kosmopolita swojego narodu", *Jewish History Quarterly*, ed. Jan Doktor et al., Vol 4 (Warsaw: Jewish Historical Institute, December 2002) p. 473.

⁷² Having said that, it must be noted that in the provinces, small Esperanto clubs were often initiated by the Jews, who, in the provinces, were mostly small-town professionals and minor intelligentsia. For example, in 1931, in a small town Orli in Bielsk Podlaski area, not far from Zamenhof's birthplace, 21 out of 24 local esperantists had Jewish names

were Protestant, however, fully dedicated to the Polish cause. Włodzimierz Pfeiffer, the renowned bookkeeper and chronicler of Esperanto movement in Łódź, despite his Evangelical faith and German origin, refused, later on during WW2 to sign a Volkslist, emphasizing his sense of national belonging.⁷³ In a country where any non-Catholic and definitely non-Christian voices were not quite of the same value as the “proper”, Catholic ones, these people were certainly able to reaffirm their identity and express their genuine concern for the country on par with their Catholic counterparts. This, yet again, proves that Polishness was more elitist and based on class, rather than ethnicity, in line with the historical tradition of what Ilya Prizel calls an “aristocratic democracy”.⁷⁴

2.5 Conclusion

In conclusion, patriotism was the key driving factor among the Poles who pursued Esperanto before 1939. The need for self-determination before 1918 and later for unifying and consolidating the diverse society of Poland was superior to that of uniting mankind under a green flag. As Ulrich Lins observes, it was a Pole, Kazimierz Bein, who insisted in 1905 upon forming a Worldwide Esperantist League, despite possible persecutions. To Poles, Esperanto was a means to an end, a language of opportunity and without international support they feared this new

and were listed as tailors or teachers, with little ethnic Polish presence. See: Zbigniew Romaniuk, „Esperantyści na terenie powiatu bielskiego do 1939 roku”, *Bielski Almanach Historyczny* (Bielsk Podlaski, 2017), pp. 213-216.

⁷³ Benedykt Wandachowicz, „Włodzimierz Pfeiffer – kreatywny księgarz i dokumentalista”, *BIBiK Biuletyn Informacji Bibliotecznych i Kulturalnych Wojewódzkiej i Miejskiej Biblioteki Publicznej w Łodzi*, nr 10 (Łódź: 19 September 2011) p. 14. <http://skany.wbp.lodz.pl/pliki/bibik/bibik_123/bibik_123.pdf>. Accessed March 2020.

⁷⁴ Prizel, *National...*, p. 40.

initiative would fail.⁷⁵ Lins, however, is wrong in ascribing these patriotic tendencies to Poles or “East Europeans”. As I will discuss in the next chapter, Esperanto at the time was a voice for the voiceless across all Europe, a platform for forgotten communities swallowed by colonial giants. Although today, more attention is given to a-national organisations like SAT, one of the Esperanto slogans of the time was “United in Diversity”, very much like today’s European Union, a platform which guarantees, promotes and protects linguistic – and other – freedoms. Therefore, patriotism shall be the leitmotif of my next chapter.

⁷⁵ Lins, *Dangerous Language*, p. 22.

CHAPTER 2

Esperanto as a means of furthering the Polish cause

3.1 Introduction

Most of the authors writing on the subject of Esperanto today, depict it as a supranational movement, aiming to connect people above such trivial divisions as national borders, class, religion etc. This, indeed, seemed to be the intention of Esperanto's creator. At the first International Congress of Esperanto in Boulogne-sur-Mer, the inventor of the language, Ludwik Zamenhof, emphasised the universal, neutral position of the language: "Within the hospitable walls of Boulogne-sur-Mer, we are not witnessing a meeting of French with English, Russians with Poles, but of human beings with human beings"⁷⁶, he proclaimed. As a result, Esperanto today is inadvertently associated with internationalism and politically, with more liberal, not to say leftist worldview. As a result, in the seminal works on the subject written by Roberto Garvía and Esther Schor, largely disproportionate attention is given to SAT, the a-national Esperanto movement led by a Marxist, Eugène Adam, aka Lanti.⁷⁷ Having read these works, one is left with a lasting impression that Esperanto mostly attracted liberals, Marxists, utopian dreamers, "pacifists, taylorists, feminists" and vegetarians in Roberto Garvia's words, trying to create an "imagined community"⁷⁸ deprived of any national divisive features, thus actively promoting world peace, harmony and human co-existence. Although it is true that Zamenhof, who later invented a brand new ideology of Homoranism, based on universal humanity, and saw universalism as a viable

⁷⁶ Qtd in Korzhenkov, *The Life...*, p. 42.

⁷⁷ See Garvía, *Esperanto...*, p. 1, pp. 123-125; Schor, pp. 141-192.

⁷⁸ Garvia, *Esperanto...*, p. 91.

solution for the future of European Jews and humanity at large, did “concentrate his energies on community building”⁷⁹ this was not necessarily the case with all Esperanto users at the time.

On the contrary, in the Europe of empires, Esperanto, with its assumption of linguistic – and general – equality, enjoyed a great degree of interest from marginalised communities, yearning for international recognition. Its promise of a free, universal and equal platform to amplify unheard voices, attracted linguistic and other minority groups, such as Scots, Catalans and Poles, who very often saw in Esperanto a pathway to linguistic and national emancipation. In this chapter, I am going to argue that Esperanto in Poland was primarily used to promote Polish interests, language, culture and, after 1918, the re-emerging nation on the world stage.

3.2 “Small nations”

From 1795 until 1918, Poland, as an independent state, disappeared from the map of Europe, its territory torn apart between three imperial partitioners: Russia, Prussia, and the Hapsburg Empire. With varying degrees of autonomy in each partition throughout this 123-year period, after each unsuccessful uprising, the Polish culture, language and the sense of nationhood were being systemically erased and fought back against by the partitioning powers. These repressions were particularly severe in the Russian and Prussian/German partitions, their severity directly proportionate to the resistance of the local population and as a direct form of punishment for the participation in national uprisings. At universities, Polish language and culture were either

⁷⁹ Ibid.

suppressed or entirely banned, Polish schools closed down, the Prussians were pursuing active politics of de-nationalisation of the Polish territories by exchanging populations⁸⁰, sending German settlers and depicting local Polish nobility as inferior. On the other hand, the Russians were trying to incorporate the “Western Gubernia” by appealing to the sense of pan-Slavism. From that perspective, Catholic, Latinised Poland was seen a “Judas of the Slavic world” and so attempts were made to Russify the Polish language by replacing the Latin alphabet with Cyrillic.⁸¹ The intellectual goods were robbed, such as the collection of the famous Załuski Library, transferred after the Kościuszko Uprising of 1794 in its entirety to St Petersburg.⁸² Only Galicia, i.e. the territories in the Austro-Hungarian partition, was given a degree of relative autonomy, at the same time, introducing laws severely deteriorating the conditions of the peasant. The persecutions of Polishness took an especially bad turn in the second part of the 19th century: after the failed January Uprising of 1961 against the Tsar, and after the German Reunification under Otto von Bismarck, who actively implemented the politics of “Kulturkampf” of which Catholic Poles were “the most convincing, undisputable motive”.⁸³

In this atmosphere, Esperanto was born. The Poles quickly saw a chance to utilise the new, still unsuspecting, language to their own means. The international links Esperanto had to offer were priceless considering Poland had neither its own government nor foreign representation at

⁸⁰ For example, German teachers were sent to Polish territories and Polish teachers sent to Germany, see: Jan Wnęk, “Problemy polskiego szkolnictwa zaboru pruskiego i rosyjskiego na kartach ‘Szkoły’ 1868-1914”, *Biuletyn Historii Wychowania* (March 2019) p.27.

⁸¹ Adam Tycner, “Cyrilica nad Wisłą”, *Rzeczpospolita*, 19 May 2012 <<https://www.rp.pl/artykul/876299-Cyrilica-nad-Wisla.html>> Accessed 10 March 2020.

⁸² Piotr Stefan Wandycz, *The Lands of Partitioned Poland, 1795-1918*. E-book, Seattle: University of Washington Press, 1984, p.22. <https://hdl-handle-net.ezproxy.st-andrews.ac.uk/2027/heb.05069>. Accessed 26 Sep 2020.

⁸³ Bornkamm, Heinrich qtd in Blanke, Richard. “The Polish Role in the Origin of Kulturkampf in Prussia.” *Canadian Slavonic Papers / Revue Canadienne des Slavistes*. Vol. 25, No. 2 (June 1983). p.254

the time. It is therefore little wonder that it was the Poles, who most energetically agitated for the creation of an international Esperanto body⁸⁴, knowing well, that any initiative taken by the Polish nation alone, in separation from the rest of Europe, might be very quickly nipped in the bud by the suspicious imperial rulers. The creation of UEA (Universala Esperanto-Asocio), a transnational governing body headquartered in Paris and presiding over local Esperanto clubs, offered a degree of protection, legitimising the movement, and at the same time providing an easy excuse for accumulating international clout.

Poles were indeed not alone in their hope for emancipation through Esperanto. The matter was of utmost importance to all “children of small nations”⁸⁵ as Patrick Parker referred to the minority nations in his 1909 article for *Tutmonda Espero*, the Catalonian Esperanto magazine. In the article, the Irish Esperantist with his Gaelic mother tongue in mind, proposed to “create, using Esperanto, a universal league for the defence and conservation of our threatened languages.”⁸⁶ Such a league, in Parker’s view, would mutually encourage the members of what he calls “small nations” to fight for their rights and international recognition in the spirit of fraternity and a sense of a common goal. “As we aim to create a big family, we mustn’t forget our origins”⁸⁷, he argued. Predictably, the Catalonian side responded with enthusiasm, highlighting the potential of Esperanto to “defend” national languages.⁸⁸ Later, in 1912, a Catalonian writer expressed his indignation at the fact that during the 1911 congress in Antwerp, his Catalan name was misspelt

⁸⁴ Lins, *Dangerous Language*, p.11.

⁸⁵ Patrick Parker, ‘Mother tongues and Esperanto’, *Tutmonda Espero*, No. 17 (May 1909), p. 70.

⁸⁶ *Ibid* p. 70.

⁸⁷ *Ibid* p. 70: “What is the goal of Esperantism? To bring people together...”

⁸⁸ *Ibid* p. 71.

and the Catalanian representation was seated together with Basques and Castilians, despite major linguistic differences.⁸⁹

As much as the Catalanian or Irish side's argument lay primarily with the question of linguistic rights, in the Polish case, the stakes were much higher. While before 1918, *Pola Esperantisto* was primarily used to promote Polish culture and literature, after regaining independence, it was not rare to come across political articles, defending Poland's territorial rights.⁹⁰ The Poles were faced with an existential question, a question of national survival, the right to existence, which, after 1918, turned into a bold promotion of the re-emergent country on the international stage. Most importantly, however, it was a question of reasserting Poland's place, position, influence, and role in Europe.

3.3 Drafting a country: Esperanto in partitioned Poland

“Take Poles, for example. Give them, instead of the Polish dialect (*‘Polskago gowora’*) – Esperanto, and you won't find in them a single Slavic trait”⁹¹. Such is the conclusion of a 1913 Russian article from a ~~Kyevan~~ paper *Nowoje Wremie* quoted in an article in *Nowy Kurjer Łódzki*. The article, titled “Dangerous Esperanto”, gives a word of warning to Russians, who, in the author's view, should see Esperanto as a vital threat to pan-Slavism, Slavic tribalism, and, by favouring Western Catholicism and Austria, a harm to Russian interests. It emphasises the growing

⁸⁹ Frederic Pujulà i Vallès, ‘Pri... escepto, kiun oni faris en Antverpeno por katalunoj’, *Kataluna Esperantisto*, No. 24 (March 1912), pp. 385-386. URL: [https://bibliotekoj.org/literaturamondo/ke1/KE024\(1912-03\).pdf](https://bibliotekoj.org/literaturamondo/ke1/KE024(1912-03).pdf)

⁹⁰ See PE: „Libroj kaj Gazetoj”, June-July 1924, p.64.

⁹¹“Niebezpieczne Esperanto”, *Nowy Kurjer Łódzki*, Nr 171 (Łódź, 28 July 1913), p.3.

use of Esperanto by the Roman Catholic Church to illustrate its claim. As much as *Nowy Kurjer Łódzki* might have ridiculed the Russian claims, there was certainly a lot of truth in the fact that Poles had actively fought back russification attempts, had always seen themselves as part of the “West”, and that Esperanto was cleverly used to reassert that position.

Under the partitions, this was done through the promotion of Polish language and culture. The *Pola Esperantisto* circles, led by the Polish intellectual elites of the time, very visibly and with plenty of enthusiasm picked up on the positivistic spirit of the epoch. Indeed, in today’s term, the Polish Esperanto movement of that time could easily be characterised as a “grassroots movement”. Decentralised and mostly powered by the hard work, engagement and activism of its members, the mainstream Polish Esperantists had a full understanding that the fate of Poland – and themselves – could be influenced by their club activity, conveniently hidden behind the green banner of Esperanto. That bottom-up initiative was best verbalised through the publication’s motto: “Czyń każdy w swoim kółku, co każe duch Boży, a całość sama się złoży”/”Let everyone do in their circle what the Spirit commands, and the pieces will come together.”⁹² This indeed could have been a clever allusion to the partitioned Poland coming together in the end. The reference to the Holy Spirit is also not without a meaning. In Catholicism, among the gifts of the Holy Spirit are wisdom, knowledge and understanding, and it is the Holy Spirit that Catholics pray to before studying. It therefore epitomises learning and education. As I explained in the previous chapter, the Polish Esperantists of the time were mainly intellectuals, scientists and educators. They understood the significance of elite creation and enlightenment for the Polish cause and were keen embracing Esperanto as a seemingly innocent means to their end, which was to create and consolidate a free, educated class of Poles, confident of their position in Europe, actively contributing their talent,

⁹² PE: Jan – Feb 2011, p. 28.

vision and ideas as equal partners, who can represent their nation internationally and speak up in its defence.

All this was conducted very much in tune with what the leading figures of the time recommended: starting at the foundations of the society, aka “organic work”: including peasants, women and ethnic minorities. This certainly was at least attempted by Esperantist. They keenly published Esperanto translations of the works of Polish women including Maria Konopnicka⁹³, an early Polish feminist Narcyza Żmichowska, or Eliza Orzeszkowa⁹⁴ and included quite a few women among their ranks. They published a few works, which, in a romantic fashion, referenced the Ukrainian folklore, and the Kozak tradition, most notably fragments of the epic poem “Maria. A Ukrainian tale” by Antoni Malczewski.⁹⁵ As mentioned in the previous chapter, despite its distinctly Polish character, the Esperanto movement circled around *Pola Esperantisto* attracted many Jewish members, with Zamenhof himself being the editor-in-chief of the magazine until 1914. And even though, the Esperantists probably never really reached out to peasants, they certainly saw Esperanto as “a blessing for the people, without excluding those with basic

⁹³ Maria Konopnicka was a renowned Polish writer of her time an author of children’s literature, as well as dramatic portrayals of ethnic and class inequalities in Poland. Her ambiguous sexuality is currently an object of discussion, as she spent many years of her life living with Maria Dulębianka, a never-married feminist activist who liked to dress in men clothes. What might seem like a paradox in our polarised times, Konopnicka also authored deeply patriotic poems, such as “Rota”, which today in one of the anthems of Polish ultra-nationalists. For more information on the debate surrounding Konopnicka’s sexuality, see Jodi C. Greig, *The Sandbox of History: Nationality, Sexuality, and the Historical Impulse in Contemporary Polish LGBTQ Culture* (University of Michigan, 2016) pp. 78-85 <https://deepblue.lib.umich.edu/bitstream/handle/2027.42/133479/jcgreig_1.pdf?isAllowed=y&sequence=1>.

⁹⁴ Like Konopnicka, Orzeszkowa was a renowned writer and one of the leading figures of Positivism in Poland. She was an advocate for women’s emancipation and right to work and be useful to a society. At the same time, she valued family above all else. For more information on Eliza Orzeszkowa’s views on feminism, please see: Eliza Orzeszkowa, *Kilka słów o kobietach* (Lviv: A. J. O. Rogosz, 1873).

⁹⁵ PE: Jan 1908, p. 12.

education”⁹⁶ and a tool more useful to the common folk “who emigrate year by year”⁹⁷ than to “a typical Warsaw-dweller who does not venture beyond his city even in his thoughts.”⁹⁸

Even though the early Polish Esperantists certainly shared and embraced progressive ideas ahead of their time and appreciated the value of diversity, they did not actively promote liberal or universalist ideas in any sense. While an occasional article from *America Esperantisto* extolling the virtues and ethics of vegetarianism might have been published⁹⁹, an article on the same subject by a Polish author was far more sceptical of a meatless diet.¹⁰⁰ While the works of feminist authors were included, they were mostly selected based on their patriotic virtue, and there was hardly any presence of agitation for women’s rights. Minority issues were not discussed on the pages of *Pola Esperantisto*, and no Jewish, German, Russian or Ukrainian materials were publicised. In terms of minorities, the magazine clearly supported assimilation over tolerance. One example of this was the decision to publish the translation of *Meir Ezofowicz* by Eliza Orzeszkowa. The novel openly promoted the assimilation of the Polish Jewry, an idea Zamenhof could not reconcile with. When initially asked to translate the work, he refused and chose to translate another work of Orzeszkowa, the novel *Marta*, themed around women’s role in the society.¹⁰¹ Finally, it is worth pointing out that the Polish Esperanto Association drew a distinct line separating itself from any other Esperanto clubs. In 1911, *Pola Esperantisto* published a note explaining that the closing of the Russian

⁹⁶ PE: Dec 1911, p. 186.

⁹⁷ PE: Jun-July 1910, p.99.

⁹⁸ Ibid.

⁹⁹ PE: Jan-Feb 1911, p. 10.

¹⁰⁰ PE: Jul-Sep 1907, p.38.

¹⁰¹ Żelazny, ”Ludwik Zamenhof – kosmopolita swojego narodu” p. 473.

Esperanto club “Liga” had “nothing to do” with the Poles and that the shutdown club had been run by “Esperantists-Russians”¹⁰².

As mentioned in the previous chapter, Polish Esperantists never had any pretension of being cosmopolitans nor dreamed of united mankind. The very idea was looked down upon as being “against human nature”¹⁰³ and something patriotic Polish Esperantists definitely did not strive to achieve. They were idealists, nonetheless, who saw and fully appreciated the value of the common language, but whose idealism was deeply rooted in their love of the country, a sense of enlightened patriotism, and the will to communicate with other nations in order to “understand their spirit”¹⁰⁴ and fulfil the historical progress of humanity.

The 1911 International Esperanto Congress in Antwerp was thus an occasion to celebrate “unity in diversity” and was reported on in much more detail than any other international congress. Among almost forty nations, the first-page report in *Pola Esperantisto* enumerates “Scots, Catalans, Basques, Maltese”¹⁰⁵, stressing that the Congress allowed each of them their own representation. The event clearly made Poles feel at home among other “small nations” and bond over hopes for national liberation. The report pays particular attention to the standing ovation received by the Flemish play *Kaatje*, which sang praises to the love of motherland, thus “manifesting they (Esperantists – author’s note) are not cosmopolitans.”¹⁰⁶ It later goes on to describe the beauty of the national dress the representatives of each country wore, rejoicing the fact that Antwerp was a place where diversity was not lost. By their bold, yet open-minded,

¹⁰² PE: Dec 1911, p. 198.

¹⁰³ Ibid.

¹⁰⁴ “Miłość Ojczyzny a Esperanto”. PE: Jul-Aug 1909, p.120.

¹⁰⁵ PE: Sept 1911, p. 134.

¹⁰⁶ PE: Sept 1911, p. 134.

embrace of nationalism and taking the central position between “cosmopolitans” and “chauvinists”, Esperantists, with their passion for education, tolerance, ethics and progress, saw themselves as true patriots and the voice of reason.

In partitioned Poland, the learning of Esperanto, was indeed, on many occasions, presented as a “patriotic duty” or a “task to fulfil”. The first argument used to promote Esperanto amongst Poles was that of linguistic equal rights. This is what the Academic Esperanto Society in Kraków and the Technical Esperanto Group from Lviv wrote in their open letter to the Polish youth:

(...) We forgot one reason why Esperanto should be enthusiastically welcomed, especially by our nation. It deprives certain nations of the privileged position of their tongues in the history of mankind, equating them with the languages of handicapped nations, to which we admittedly belong to. *Neither a German nor a Frenchman nor an Englishman learns Polish, so why should we waste our abilities and our time on studying French declensions or English phrases?*

Therefore, if an idea, whose realisation will give us equal rights and liberate our energies from the serfdom (of having to learn another language – author’s note), has appeared, then it is *our patriotic duty* to rush to meet this idea.¹⁰⁷

¹⁰⁷ PE: Jan-Feb 1911, p.3.

As we can see, the diminished status of dominant languages at the time, such as English, French, or German would not only position the Polish language on the same level as its European counterparts, but also make these other, larger nations - or even empires - learn a language born on the Polish soil. “Let’s learn Esperanto and we’ll have more energy to learn our own mother tongue”¹⁰⁸, proclaimed A. Lange in his 1908 article for *Pola Esperantisto*, suggesting Esperanto as a handy replacement for Russian and German in foreign language learning. After all, as another article concludes, it would be “unnatural” for anyone who considers themselves Polish to reject Esperanto, as it would “deny them the self-preservation instincts and the political intelligence.”¹⁰⁹ This clearly proves the political dimension of learning Esperanto as a means to serve Poland and ensuring its historical course is right on track.

The second argument was that of a “civilisational mission”. From its very beginning, Esperanto was perceived as an invention, which had been, on many occasions, compared to other modern creations of the time, such as the locomotive¹¹⁰, or the printing press. “Homeless” Poles from a non-existent state, saw and understood the pressing call of modernity, and an international language invented “on the Polish soil” was one way to answer it, without being openly rebellious towards the partitioning powers. They quickly realised they had something relevant, original and innovative to offer, and were keen to promote it as a native export.

Esperanto was thus marketed as a product “made in Poland”, a gift to the world “thrown from above the Polish-Lithuanian fields”,¹¹¹ and Ludwik Zamenhof was depicted as “a Genius

¹⁰⁸ PE Jan 1908, p. 4.

¹⁰⁹ PE: Dec 1911, p. 186.

¹¹⁰ “Język na polskiej zrodzony ziemi”. PE: Jul-Aug, 1911, p. 110.

¹¹¹ “Język na polskiej zrodzony ziemi”. PE: Jul-Aug 1911, p.109.

born on the Polish soil”¹¹², a great inventor, the bearer of light, and very often spoke of in Promethean terms. As one of the leading Esperantists of the time, Antoni Grabowski, pointed out, by introducing Esperanto to the world, not only did Poles regain their dignity, by not having to speak “privileged” languages any more, but most importantly, ceased to be “the parrot of nations”, making a valuable and original contribution to the world.¹¹³ Promoting Esperanto was, in this sense, a thinly veiled attempt at emphasising Poland’s role in Europe, taking (back) its “righteous” place, on par with other, legitimate European nations, and proving its relevance and perhaps even historicity, despite having no place on the map.

Esperanto was also seen as a way of liberating Poland from foreign influences, German in particular. In an article in *Gazeta Łódzka* from 1912, Władysław Wojciechowicz, an Esperantist from Łódź, bitterly argues that German had become a local language in Poland, that Germans can be found everywhere, and all the western cultural influences come to Poland through Berlin to the extent that “should the Germans decide to close their border, we would become helpless.”¹¹⁴ Esperanto in this context was meant to facilitate Poland’s cultural and economic independence and free Polish people from the “supremacy of our lovely neighbours”¹¹⁵ or any other foreign nation. In Wojciechowicz’s view, the internationalism of Esperanto would benefit the Polish economy. In a multicultural, multi-ethnic industrial hub as Łódź, Wojciechowicz’s vision clearly made a lot of sense. Łódź was at the time a meeting place between cultures, “the Manchester of the East”, a

¹¹² Ibid, p. 110.

¹¹³ PE: Nov-Dec 1910, p. 144.

¹¹⁴ Władysław Wojciechowicz. “Esperanto wobec najogólniejszych zagadnień narodowych.” *Gazeta Łódzka* (Łódź, 24 July 1912). In Pfeiffer, Włodimierz. *Kronika Esperantystów Łódzkich*. Biblioteka Uniwersytetu Łódzkiego. 5005/2.

¹¹⁵ Ibid.

place of local and international migration.¹¹⁶ By bridging the gap between East and West, Esperanto was meant to help Poland become a transportation and industrial hub right in the heart of Europe, thus allowing the country realise its full potential and rip the benefits of its geographical location.

“Both those who respect us and those who hate us will speak it (Esperanto – author’s note)”¹¹⁷, wrote D-ro Ostrowski in his article titled *A language born on the Polish soil* in 1911, each time italicising the *born on the Polish soil* phrase, which he used six times. It is open to interpretation who exactly he meant by “those who hate us”, but it can easily be assumed that identifying the language as, first and foremost, a Polish product, he could have been referring not only to the general critics of Esperanto, but to the partitioning empires, whose languages – Russian and German – he would hope to replace with Esperanto. The way in which he is referring to the Esperantists as “workers of Tomorrow”¹¹⁸ also bears a lot of significance, cleverly intertwining the progressive spirit of the time with the burning hope for the much desired Polish independence, thus highlighting the role of Esperantists as those Poland’s future depended on.

The choice of works published in Esperanto offers a lot of insight into how devoted the *Pola Esperantisto* crew to emphasising the Polishness of Esperanto. For an educated Polish speaker, it is indeed delightful to look at the selection of the most popular Polish writers and poets, including Adam Mickiewicz, Juliusz Słowacki, Henryk Sienkiewicz, Maria Konopnicka, Eliza Orzeszkowa, Kazimierz Przerwa-Tetmajer, Adam Asnyk, Julian Tuwim, Aleksander Fredro,

¹¹⁶ For more information about the city of Łódź, see Winson Chu. “The ‘Lodzermensch’: From Cultural Contamination to Marketable Multiculturalism.” *Germany, Poland and Postmemorial Relations: In Search of a Livable Past*. Ed. Kopp, Kristin, and Niżyńska, Joanna. Palgrave Macmillan, (2012): 239-258.

¹¹⁷ “Język na polskiej zrodzony ziemi”. PE: Jul-Aug 1911, p.109.

¹¹⁸ Ibid. p.110.

Leopold Staff among many others. It, however, worth noticing the virtual absence (with a few notable exceptions, such as Goethe) of foreign authors. It is, moreover, worth noting, that while all of the above Polish authors were extremely prolific, the choice of the works was deliberate. Let us look at Adam Mickiewicz's "The Books of the Polish People and of the Polish Pilgrimage". This position remains a lesser known work by Mickiewicz, and certainly far less entertaining than some of the other texts he produced. Yet, it is what the Esperantists felt was right to publish at the time. The text, gospel-like in style, presents the trope of Poland as the Christ of Nations, whose mission is to raise from the dead and save Europe.¹¹⁹ The experience and the suffering of the Polish émigrés in foreign lands serves as a lesson in humility and tolerance, which is to be used later to create a Europe of free and equal nations. This certainly was a goal Esperanto could pave the way to. By including this particular fragment from Mickiewicz, the Esperantists revealed they saw Poland as a future possible leader of Christendom, peace-bringer and even the saviour of the divided continent.

This morally justified, messianic vision was deeply rooted in the country's Catholic tradition. Papal letters and opinions on Esperanto were widely published, Papal blessings and stamps of approval deeply valued. Esperanto was heavily advertised by academics, lauding it for the creation of a European student network. These facts emphasise the relatively narrow socio-cultural background of the leading Polish Esperantists, represented by the Catholic, educated noble elites and assimilated minorities. Yet, this elitism finds its justification in history. As Ilya Prizel

¹¹⁹ Adam Mickiewicz was a Romantic poet and is, until today, considered "the national bard" of Poland. His concept of Polish messianism was first laid out in his play "Dziady" ("The Forefathers' Eve") written after the fall of the November uprising of 1830-1831. In his vision, Poland was meant to lead the way in Europe, "Verily I say unto you, it is not for you to learn civilization from foreigners, but it is you who are to teach them civilization... You are among the foreigners like the Apostles among the idolaters" (qtd in Prizel, p.41).

observes, in Positivism, the notion of Polishness was seen in terms of “civilisational” efforts, with the aim of fully assimilating the multi-ethnic Eastern Borderlands. As he observes, “they would be united, not by class, but by the superiority of Polish culture and would be defined by Polish language and customs.”¹²⁰ It is therefore clear that in this context, Polishness became a narrow privilege, reserved for the patriotic, educated, Polish-speaking, ideally Roman Catholic elite.

Yet, this was exactly the brand of Polishness the *Pola Esperantisto* circles would promote. One might wonder why so many assimilated Jews, polonised Germans or Lutheran Poles would be so eager to sign up to this agenda. It could be the case that, to many, Polish nationalism seemed more digestible and liberal than Russian, Prussian or Austrian imperialisms. Perhaps, many were hoping to be able to shape the reborn country to their own liking. Either way, it becomes obvious that Esperanto played a representative role and in the land of hybrid identities one had to make a decision and that innocent, plucky, long-suffering Polishness was perhaps the most hopeful option available.

The 1912 International Congress of Esperanto in Kraków was, again, a way to showcase the potential of not only Kraków but the Polish culture. The visitors to Poland’s old capital had a chance to enjoy Moniuszko’s operas and lay laurels at the Mickiewicz’s monument in the Main Square, as well as to listen to a Catholic sermon later. Again, the congress was a typical display of Polish class-bound patriotism, and an opportunity for Esperantists to mingle with European elites, playing a “rare role of host among the West.”¹²¹

¹²⁰ Prizel, *National Identity...*, p. 40.

¹²¹ PE: April 1912, p. 58.

3.4 Nationalising Esperanto

After a period of inactivity caused by WWI and later the Polish-Bolshevik War of 1919-1920, the Polish Esperanto Movement restarted its activity, this time in an independent nation. At last, the Esperantists did not have to use half-measures and euphemisms to express their patriotic leanings. As a fully-fledged state, Poland became the official “cradle of Esperanto” and could use the international language not only to promote Polish literary and cultural achievements, but also for political gain.

The newly found sense of identity was clearly manifested in the very first post-independence publications of *Pola Esperantisto*. Esperanto became a tool of justice, something this long-suffering nation had hungered for so long. In 1922, the magazine declared that having suffered from the hands of others, Poland wants to work towards a just and happy future.¹²² Indeed, Esperantists did not desire to hold grudges against its neighbours, but were certainly willing to restart international cooperation in order to regain and strengthen their position, significance, power and influence among in Western Europe and carry out its civilisational mission in the East. Esperanto was one of the means to help achieve that. This 1919 speech at a Warsaw Esperanto Society meeting in which Dr Emilian Loth, an Esperantist from Pabianice near Łódź, expresses the sentiment best:

(...) The resurrection of Poland is not only the annihilation of violent partitions, it imposes on us far-reaching responsibilities. We are supposed to become a factor of political balance in the East of Europe, a hub of the western civilisation. We must

¹²² PE: December 1922, p.3.

revive fine traditions of Rzeczpospolita, which marched in the front lines of noble progress. We must end the 18th cent. habit of copying the West in every matter, we must prove our ability for creative life and own initiative. We should march not behind, but amongst the ranks of Western nations. A necessary condition for this postulate is to increase our interest in the factors of cultural development and in new ideas. Our role, the role of Polish Esperantists, is to work together with nations of the Western culture in promoting and spreading the international language, an auxiliary second language to all, lest we live to be ashamed, should Esperanto, which came out of Warsaw, come back to us through Paris and London.¹²³

Esperanto was indeed this brand new, innovative idea, which could put Poland on the map not only geographically, but culturally, economically, and politically. As such, Esperanto quickly became “nationalised” and followed the mainstream political sentiments of the time. After the Bolshevik invasion, Polish Esperantists were quick to spell out their anti-communist attitude. In 1923, in an article titled “Grava Dangers”, Grave Danger, the author emphasises the right of every “true” Esperantist to protest should anyone try to “smuggle” any utopian ideas such as “a-nationalism, socialism, communism or pacifism”¹²⁴ under the green banner. Comparing and contrasting, via Esperanto, oneself with other nations was meant to better shape and develop national identity.¹²⁵ Later that year, the magazine published a Poznań Declaration, in which the

¹²³ Emilian Loth’s speech, 1919. Archiwum Państwowe w Łodzi. Archiwum Dr Emiliana Lotha Inżyniera Chemika w Pabianicach. Przemówienia na uroczystościach, zebraniach, odczytach, notatki z podróży zagranicznych. 1914-1939. Sygnatura 8.

¹²⁴ PE: Feb-March 1923, p. 83.

¹²⁵ PE: April 1923, p. 92.

Polish Esperanto Society declared that “at each and every opportunity they shall serve the national interest of Poland, be it by the information sent abroad, forging international friendships, connecting it to the allies in the West, or debunking the slander of its enemies.”¹²⁶

The Polish Esperantists took their new mission seriously. One example includes the riposte to *The Wreck of Europe*, a book by the a former Italian Prime Minister, Francesco Saverio Nitti, in which the author severely criticised Poland’s attempts at creating an empire despite all its weakness, its inability to “assimilate” the Jewish population, as well as questions the post-Versailles territorial order benefitting Poland since 1919. In his book, Nitti called the creation of the Free City of Gdańsk “absurd” and questioned such Polish acquisitions as the “Danzig corridor” and Silesia. In response to Nitti’s criticism of Poland’s alleged inability of self-rule, the Esperantists published a 13-page long article, shooting down Nitti’s arguments one by one. The article refers to the distant history, emphasising that the Danzig corridor is *tute Pola*, all Polish, as Prussia was never truly German. When Nitti pointed to the internal anarchy in Poland, the Esperantists reminded the reader of how Polish military defended Europe from Bolshevism and the Tatar hordes. When Nitti called the Free City of Gdańsk the hometown of Schopenhauer, the Esperantists reminded him that the immediate predecessors of Schopenhauer wanted the city to be Polish, that Poles are only the city’s custodians and respect the German language and minority rights.¹²⁷

A similar, defensive tone, aiming to right the wrong and punish the slanderers, can be felt at an article published in response to Lithuanian Esperantists’ “lies” allegedly present in pamphlets which were openly distributed during the Nuremberg Congress, in which Lithuanians accused

¹²⁶ PE: May -June 1923, p. 111.

¹²⁷ PE: June-July, 1924, p. 67-69.

Poles of police harassment.¹²⁸ The Polish Esperantists vehemently denied these claims, at the same time making a statement trying to prove the cultural Polishness of Lithuania, and justify the presence of Poles in the region. Through this example the inseparability of the chief Esperanto voices in Poland and the general Polish policy of colonising and “civilising” its easternmost regions becomes evident.

This political twist was present even among the ranks of scouts. In interwar Poland, the Polish Scouting and Guiding Association - Związek Harcerstwa Polskiego (ZHP) was a core patriotic youth organisation based on the ideas of Robert Baden-Powell, the English founder of scouting. The aim of ZHP was to train future soldiers and defenders of Poland in the spirit of patriotism, abstinence and sportsmanship.¹²⁹ Emil Mayer was the most active Esperantist of the movement, intensely engaged in promoting Esperanto among fellow scouts.¹³⁰ In his report to the Head of the Polish Scouting Movement, the top Esperantist-scout, Mayer, boasted about writing a riposte to the Ukrainian scouts, who, in the Paris Esperanto publication “Scolta Heroldo”, published a piece aimed at Poles entitled “Harm done to Ukrainian Scouts in Poland.” Mayer, not exactly in the spirit of peace and brotherhood, responded with an article titled: “Brazen lies of Ukrainian scouts in front of the whole worlds.”¹³¹

In this atmosphere, in the country where ethnic Poles had a rather narrow majority, divisions became inevitable. Zamenhof’s daughter, Lidia, decided to open her own club,

¹²⁸ PE: Jan-Feb, 1924, p.12.

¹²⁹ For more information of scouting in Poland, please see: Leszek Rysak, “Początki Harcerstwa”, *Biuletyn Instytutu Pamięci Narodowej*, nr 5/6/2010 < http://ipn.gov.pl/_data/assets/pdf_file/0018/62550/1-24736.pdf> Accessed March 2020.

¹³⁰ See: Emil Mayer, *Esperanto i jego zadania* (Kraków: Juna Esperantisto, 1934).

¹³¹ Archiwum Akt Nowych. Archiwum Związku Harcerstwa Polskiego. *Esperanto [korespondencja w sprawie propagowania Esperanto]*. Report ”Do Naczelnika Harcerstwa Polskiego”, 13 Nov 1931. Sygnatura 1481.

Konkordo, which had more universal interpretation of interna ideo and followed the doctrine of Homoranism. Other, regional clubs with mostly Jewish membership opened up under a close scrutiny of the police.¹³² Finally, Polish Socialist Esperantists opened their own club, “Laboro” and published on Esperanto in working-class newspapers and magazines, such as *Łodzianin* or *Nowy Czas*.

International Esperanto congresses played an important political role in interwar Poland and were directly linked to the country’s foreign policy. The Esperantists keenly toed the political line to represent their country with dignity at home and abroad. Before the 1926 International Congress in Edinburgh, for example, Polish Esperantists felt that it was their “civic duty” to “disrupt” the plans to hold the next congress in Gdańsk.¹³³ They feared the Germans would hijack the event and use it to their advantage.¹³⁴ Similarly, the Polish Esperantists refused to attend the 1933 Cologne congress to boycott “persecutions of race and nationality” which had been taking place in Hitler’s Germany.¹³⁵

The International Congresses organised in the interwar Poland, most notably the Warsaw International Esperanto Congress of 1937 were propaganda-like in style. Poland wanted to showcase its modernity, culture and present itself on the international stage as a progressive, western nation. The country was indeed undergoing many changes in desperate and bold attempts

¹³² Archiwum Akt Nowych. Urząd Wojewódzki Lubelski. *Działalność komunistyczna*. 1928. Sygnatura 270/IV-13.

¹³³ Archiwum Akt Nowych. Ministerstwo Spraw Zagranicznych. 10 July 1926. Sygnatura 7192.

¹³⁴ The Free City of Gdańsk, the direct creation of the Treaty of Versailles, was a semi-autonomous construct and a bone of contention between interwar Poland and Germany. The city had a long and complicated past, with a predominantly German population, yet through many years loyal to Poland. To learn more on the mixed Polish-German heritage, international influences, and complex identities of the city, please see: Peter Oliver Loew, *Danzig: Biographie einer Stadt*. (Muenchen: Verlag C. H. Beck, 2011).

¹³⁵ Archiwum Akt Nowych. Ministerstwo Spraw Zagranicznych. Odo Bujwid’s Letter. 14 April 1934. Sygnatura 7207.

to shake off the phantom of a hundred and twenty-three years of partitions. As a result, it boasted significant technological, artistic, and scientific achievements. In 1929, the Polish Airlines “LOT” was created, which also provided more incentive for international travel. Luxtorpeda, a modern superfast train was another feather in the cap. Poles finally had their own representation at major sporting events, with Halina Konopacka, a Polish female discus thrower, winning gold at the 1928 Summer Olympics in Amsterdam. Polish artists, such as a silent film actress Apolonia Chałupiec, aka. Pola Negri and tenor Jan Kiepura became household names world-wide. Polish scientists were succeeding internationally, with microbiologist Ludwik Hirschfeld making important discoveries related to blood groups and mathematician Waclaw Sierpński advancing number theories. Finally, the creation of a brand-new Polish port, Gdynia, was the culmination of the Second Polish Republic’s efforts and the most palpable evidence of the country’s potential.

Indeed, the Polish President at the time of the Warsaw Congress of 1937, Ignacy Mościcki, was himself a scientist, and the Congress was proud that he decided to become the Alto Protektanto, the High Protector, of the Jubilee Congress. Esperantists were proud that through their language they could shine the light on their homeland and make Poland, “Lulilo de Esperanto” (“Cradle of Esperanto”) even more significant in the world, thus contributing and increasing the country’s success.

Esperanto was perceived as part of the country’s progress. The language was praised for the facilitation it provided for international travel and communication. Orbis, the first and most renowned Polish travel agency, advertises its services in the Congress’s brochures. On top of that, the congresses themselves served as not only linguistic gatherings, but an opportunity to explore all major Polish attractions and the Esperantists made great efforts at attracting international

attention through the publication of attractive brochures and petitioning the government to offer the foreign visitors significant travel discounts.

Despite all their efforts, the numbers were not in Esperantists' favour. The cradle of Esperanto still did not generate enough Esperanto learners and the international audiences did not attend the Polish congresses in the same numbers they attended Congress in the West.¹³⁶ Poland seemed too exotic, too Eastern, too messy, and even too dangerous for some. In 1927, *Stockholms-Tidningen*, a Swedish morning paper, for example, reported from the Polish Gdańsk-Warsaw Congress in rather negative terms, which for obvious reasons greatly worried the Polish Ministry of Foreign Affairs. The Swedish reporter clearly did not appreciate Warsaw's multiculturalism at the time. The paper describes the city as "a half-eastern"¹³⁷, which, despite the warm welcome from the Polish hosts, is full of pickpockets and does not have much to offer.

Apart from this, misery and poverty were what we witnessed. A multitude of beggars, strange figures that popped up wherever the Congress group gathered. They were terribly obtrusive and certainly wanted to rob those who were not careful. This made the stay in the Polish capital unpleasant, which could not be erased by the kindness and readiness to serve from those who received the delegates. Warsaw Jews give the town a strange character. You can see them

¹³⁶ Kongresoj database. Dr Bernhard Struck.

¹³⁷ Archiwum Akt Nowych. Poselstwo RP w Sztokholmie. *Kongres Esperantystów w Warszawie*. 16 August 1927. Sygnatura 53.

everywhere, in coats and original caps. They look poor and fanatical, and everything that has to do with cleanliness is alien to them.¹³⁸

Such unfair descriptions, considering Esperanto was invented by a Jew, and that Esperantists already had to fight domestic anti-Semites on top of the foreign ones, must have surely been a massive blow to the popularity of the movement.

Such negative attitudes of foreign observers could have been one of the reasons why, having a fantastic potential, the Polish government at the time did not devote enough attention to the Esperanto and did not take it seriously enough. Looking through the correspondence of Prof. Odo Bujwid, the editor-in-chief of *Pola Esperantisto* from 1928 on, a renowned Cracovian bacteriologist, and perhaps the most respectable face of Polish Esperantists, one can easily observe that all the initiative to use Esperanto as a platform to promote the country abroad came from the Esperantists, or to be more precise, from Prof. Bujwid himself, and *not* from the government. One particularly telling example of the government's lack of support is the letter Bujwid received from the Ministry of the Political Department before his journey to Brazil. Bujwid wanted to act as an *official* Polish representative at the 1936 Rio de Janeiro Congress and use this as an opportunity to establish relations with the Polish colonists in Parana, St Catarina, Rio Grande and Espirito Santo.¹³⁹ The Polish side, however, refused to send him as an official delegate, claiming the

¹³⁸ Ibid.

¹³⁹ Between 1870s and 1920s, Brazil attracted many Polish settlers, mostly farmers. They would usually enter the country as German or Russian subjects, but the unique Polish presence in Brazil and the cultural fusion is felt until the present day. Please see: Anna Dvorak, *A Hidden Immigration: The Geography of Polish-Brazilian Cultural Identity*, (UCLA: 2013).

government had not been formally invited, yet insisting Bujwid would act as a Polish representative anyway, “by the nature of things”¹⁴⁰.

The Polish government’s support for Esperanto was limited to issuing free passports, visas, and, occasionally, discounted public transport tickets.¹⁴¹ Left to fend for themselves, Esperantists dramatically petitioned the government and its representatives for more funds, statements of support or at least for understanding of the significance of the movement. In their letter to the Polish Embassy in Washington D.C, two renowned Esperantists: already mentioned Emilian Loth of Pabianice near Łódź and Dr Jan Mędrkiewicz from Warsaw, tried to raise awareness among the Polish representation in Washington D.C. as to the great value they claimed Esperanto had for the Polish people.

The appreciation for Esperanto is automatically associated with appreciation for its homeland, its cradle, thus bestowing the Pole with an incredible asset, which he can – and should – skilfully use abroad to promote and emphasise its civilisational services for mankind and to win support and admiration of all the nations in the world.¹⁴²

Their call did not, however, raise enough attention in the Embassy, even though the pressure on the Polish representation to step up their efforts and take its rightful ownership of

¹⁴⁰ Archiwum Akt Nowych. Ministerstwo Spraw Zagranicznych. Odo Bujwid’s letter, 1 September 1936. Sygnatura 2975.

¹⁴¹ Archiwum Akt Nowych. Ministerstwo Spraw Zagranicznych. 29 April 1934. Sygnatura 7207.

¹⁴² Archiwum Akt Nowych. Ambasada RP w Waszyngtonie. Sygnatura 1663.

Esperanto also came from the Americans. In 1933, the Esperanto Association of North America invited the Polish Ambassador in Washington, D.C., Mr Stanisław Patek, to represent the cradle of Esperanto and make a speech at an event commemorating the seventy-fourth anniversary of the birth of Zamenhof. This must have come as a surprise to the Polish representation on American soil, and a letter was sent, explaining the Ambassador was “away in Europe” and promising to send an attaché instead. In 1937, the American Esperantists sent another invitation, to a new Ambassador, Count Jerzy Potocki, this time inviting the Polish side to a Golden Jubilee Congress. The new Ambassador also turned out to be in Europe, and the Polish Embassy politely offered to send a lesser diplomat, “should (the Congress organisers) desire to have the Embassy represented.”¹⁴³ This lacklustre attitude to the promotion of Esperanto and the very fact that the Polish representation did not take their own initiative to create any commemorative events themselves and waited to be invited lets us understand why Esperanto never became a successful Polish product. It is worth noting however, that in the end, the attaché sent to make a speech, did use it to make a political point about Poland eager to learn new ideas and, in turn, “spreading western culture among her neighbors.”¹⁴⁴

3.5 Conclusion

While the lack of central policy towards Esperanto was understandable in the time of the partitions, it continued in independent Poland. As a result, the country’s Esperantists never really

¹⁴³ Ibid.

¹⁴⁴ Ibid.

utilised their chance and potential to make Esperanto a valuable Polish “export” product. Instead, the independent country failed to fully appreciate its value and market it accordingly. Although there might have been enough understanding in some circles, the Polish government was sceptical and inactive on the issue. One reason behind this scepticism, was perhaps the fact that in the Europe where anti-Semitism was on the rise, Zamenhof’s language was deemed far too dangerous, too Jewish and too Marxist to be considered a safe bet. Another reason for this failure could have been simply the lack of funds. The Polish Treasury was tasked not only with integrating the economies of the three former partitions¹⁴⁵, but also with building a new country from scratch and coping with the global recession of the 1930s.

It is, however, interesting to observe through the lens of Esperanto, the process of creating the nation. In a way it is congruent with Miroslav Hroch’s theory¹⁴⁶ of three stages: first, the movement towards nationhood is purely cultural and intellectual, then becomes more patriotic until the third stage, full mobilisation is achieved. Such was the journey of Esperanto in Poland: at first, looked at from a progressive, more cultural, and linguistic, rather than purely patriotic standpoint. Later, it became more ethnically specific, patriotic, and utilitarian. Yet, Hroch’s theory holds true only to some extent in the Polish case, as it relates to the creation of new states. We must remember that at the time, Poland was not an entirely new state, but a discontinued state, a state interrupted, which saw its rise to independence as a historical inevitability and was looking not

¹⁴⁵ Which, as Trenkler and Wolf argue, it managed quite successfully, see: Trenkler, Carsten, and Nikolaus Wolf. “Economic Integration across Borders: The Polish Interwar Economy 1921-1937.” *European Review of Economic History*, vol. 9, no. 2, 2005, pp. 199–231.

¹⁴⁶ Miroslav Hroch, *Social Preconditions of National Revival in Europe: A Comparative Analysis of the Social Composition of Patriotic Groups Among the Smaller European Nations* (New York: Columbia University Press, 2000).

only to establish itself on an international stage, but to re-establish its former glory and influence. In this context, the pressures coming from Polish multiculturalism and other “small nations” yearning to breathe free took its toll on the Esperanto movement in Poland, making it in time more insular, ethno-centric and overall challenging to reach the general audience. The movement, which by definition was transnational and universal, created too much suspicion in the population where “the Other” dwelled so close to “Us”. These challenges shall be explored in the coming chapter, *The critical voices*.

CHAPTER 3

The critical voices

4.1 Introduction

“There will be a time when the Polish soil and nation will understand what fame gave this great son of God to his homeland”¹⁴⁷ said the chief Rabbi of Warsaw, Samuel Abraham Poznański, at the funeral of the creator of Esperanto, Ludwik Lazar Zamenhof, in 1917. This wistful and, at the same time, hopeful reflection gives us clear evidence that Esperanto had not been fully understood and appreciated by Zamenhof’s countrymen at the time of his death. Indeed, it would be a mistake to assume that Esperanto reached high levels of general recognition and wider popularity at any given time in Poland. On the contrary, this strange new language was frequently an easy target of vicious attacks, sweeping generalisations and acute suspicion, as it is often the case with many unknown things and inventions. As much as this it offered a brand new ground for familiar poetry and prose to thrive on, this defamiliarization was both a source of fascination and scepticism, or even fear.

The criticism of Esperanto was persistent throughout the period described in this thesis, it came from various, sometimes most unexpected people and places and was as vitriolic as it was persistent. On the one hand, it was often bizarre, unfounded in logic, and prejudiced. On the other, it tended to reflect the general opinion and public moods, and, occasionally, it did point out to faults and contradictions among the movement and its lofty aspirations. The purpose and goals of the Esperantists were in question, and the ideology attached to it did not help to appease the critics.

¹⁴⁷ Andreas Künzli, *L.L. Zamenhof (1859-1917): Esperanto, Hillelismus (Homaranismus) und die "jüdische Frage" in Ost- und Westeuropa* (Wiesbaden, Harrassowitz Verlag, 2010), p. 322.

In this chapter, I shall analyse the common reasons and sources of this criticism. I will try to contextualise the nature and the intensity of Esperanto and draw parallels between the political milieu of the times and the reception of Esperanto in Poland.

4.2 Unwelcome linguistic competition

In pre-1918 Poland, it seems that the biggest objection was that the new “artificial” language would constitute additional competition, if not a threat, to Polish, which, due to partitions, was already deprived of its official status and had a lower standing than the languages of the partitioning powers: Russian and German¹⁴⁸, as well as the popular at the time French and English. In multicultural Łódź, the discussion on the impact of Esperanto was particularly vivid. In a series of letters to “Gazeta Łódzka” in 1912, a reader, Mr Stanisław Kaźmierczak puts forward several arguments against Esperanto. He accuses Esperantists of doing Germans a favour and becoming enemies of Poland. He undermines the very necessity for the existence of an international language claiming that first, he had never met anyone abroad who would speak Esperanto, and second, that a knowledge of any foreign language is not required to succeed, considering the number of Germans and French in Łódź, who, despite not being able to speak Polish are still more successful than Poles themselves. He accuses Esperanto of being anti-Polish and encouraging a “deluge” of

¹⁴⁸ For more on the linguistic policies in the Russian partition, please see: Weeks, Theodore R. *Nation and State in Late Imperial Russia. Nationalism and Russification on the Western Frontier, 1863-1914*. (DeKalb, Ill.: Northern Ill. Univ. Press, 1996). For Germanisation of schools in the Prussian partition, check: Chwalba, Andrzej. *Historia Polski 1795-1918*, (Kraków: 2000), pp. 183f. as well as Broszat, Martin. *Zweihundert Jahre deutsche Polenpolitik*, (München: 1963), 75-77.

the country by “foreign elements”¹⁴⁹ and Esperantists of wasting their energy and talent to translate Polish works into Esperanto rather than living languages into Polish.¹⁵⁰ He illustrates his argument by invoking the power and strength of Piast Poland¹⁵¹ of Bolesław Chrobry and Krzywousty, and the Poland of Stefan Batory, and presents it as the time when Poles spoke only their own language and Latin in public life.

(...) but when the times of cordial friendship with the neighbouring countries came, when it became fashionable to speak French, when Poles travelling abroad brought back foreign speech, then Poland, due to the decay of own customs, perished.¹⁵²

This monolithic, homogenous vision of linguistic singularity could easily be accused of being irrational and xenophobic. Yet, Stanisław Kaźmierczak fights back such arguments by giving the examples of culturally and linguistically self-contained Norway and Sweden, and presents them as success stories when compared to the “Western” countries which “spend more on prisons than

¹⁴⁹ ”Z powodu artykułu ‘Z Esperantyzmu’”. *Gazeta Łódzka* 4 July 1912 nr 121 in *Włodzimierz Pfeiffer Chronicle*.

¹⁵⁰ ”Wolna Trybuna.” *Gazeta Łódzka*. 9 July 1912 nr 129 in *Włodzimierz Pfeiffer Chronicle*.

¹⁵¹ The myth of the ethnocentric Poland under the Piast dynasty has been rooted in the Polish political debate for a long time and often compared and contrasted with the Jagiellonian Poland. I am discussing this on p. 68 of this thesis in more detail. For more reference, please see Kubera, Jacek. “Polska ‘piastowska’ vs ‘jagiellońska’; Odmienność wizji relacji z Niemcami jako determinanta poglądów na polską politykę zagraniczną.” *Acta Politica Polonica* nr 4/2016 (38).

¹⁵² “Wolna Trybuna” 15 July 1912, nr 134.

education”.¹⁵³ He also argues that while Germany, where the vast majority speaks German¹⁵⁴, can feel at ease in promoting Esperanto, partitioned, multicultural, multilingual Poland cannot afford such luxury if it wants its language to survive.

Interestingly, while Kaźmierczak seems to acknowledge and approve of the use of Latin in Poland during its glory days, the same status is not granted to Esperanto. He sees Esperanto as nothing but an inelegant jargon and believes Poles would make a grave mistake if they chose it over their native language. He goes on to compare the relationship between Polish and Esperanto to that between Hebrew and Yiddish.¹⁵⁵ At the time, Yiddish was perceived as one of the “jargons” unequal in its status to “legitimate” languages like Polish, Russian, or Hebrew. He accuses Esperanto of not having a soul, and concludes that if, after all, Poles are to learn any foreign language, it is best if they learn German, since “Germans will not plot against us in Esperanto”.¹⁵⁶

Stanisław Kaźmierczak was certainly not alone in seeing Esperanto as a rival to the Polish language. In 1897, a popular magazine for traders and industrialists, “Dźwignia”, although acknowledging the need for a unified language, recommended the learning of other Slavic

¹⁵³ ”Wolna Trybuna” 31 July 1912, nr 148.

¹⁵⁴ This was, obviously, Kaźmierczak view of Germany, which was nevertheless multilingual, considering the Danish speakers in the north, French speakers in Alsace – Lorraine and around 3 mln Polish speakers in the east, see: Hagen, William W. *Germans, Poles, and Jews: The Nationality Conflict in the Prussian East, 1772-1914*. (Chicago-London: University of Chicago Press, 1980). Having said that, Kaźmierczak does have a point in that Poland was clearly more linguistically diverse of the two, with just over 61% of Polish speakers in Warsaw in 1897; see Corrsin, Stephen D. “Language Use in Cultural and Political Change in Pre-1914 Warsaw: Poles, Jews, and Russification.” *The Slavonic and East European Review*, vol. 68, no. 1, 1990, p. 73.

¹⁵⁵ ”Wolna Trybuna” 9 July 1912, nr 129.

¹⁵⁶ ”Wolna Trybuna” 15 July 1912, nr 134.

languages instead, such as Czech.¹⁵⁷ “It would be in the interest of our country to cultivate the learning of Slavic languages among our trades”¹⁵⁸, the article suggests, as it would not only make it easier for Poles to learn another Slavic language but would also enhance trade with the Czech Republic and open the door to exports from south-eastern Europe.

Esperanto was often accused of lacking aesthetic value and depicted as a rough, unsophisticated auxiliary, rather than a literary, language. In 1916, a reputable magazine of Polish freethinkers¹⁵⁹, *Myśl Niepodległa* (Independent Thought), published an entire article in which it explained that Esperanto, despite its undeniable benefits for purely utilitarian endeavours, cannot possibly be used to create poetry, being a “stateless” language. According to the article, Esperanto was “a calculated jargon [...] a soulless fabrication, which might appeal to intellect, but will terrify any man of taste”.¹⁶⁰ Its vocabulary had been criticised as “typical of a salesman”, its poets slammed as talentless, calculated, and lacking a poetic style. “If there is no nation without a bard there is no bard without a nation”¹⁶¹ the article sums up.

In another “literary” critique from 1910, Karol Appel, a linguist, a literary scholar, and a lecturer at the University of Warsaw, called Esperanto “a truly disgusting jargon”¹⁶². He made no

¹⁵⁷ „Język handlowy oraz próby języka międzynarodowego,” *Dźwignia Przemysłowo-Handlowa Ilutrowana*, 15 June 1987, nr 12 p.80.

¹⁵⁸ Ibid.

¹⁵⁹ It is worth noting that although initially dedicated to freethinkers, this publication under Andrzej Niemojewski as editor-in-chief, slowly moved towards the right, embracing Roman Dmowski’s politics. See: Barbara Wagner, “Secularity in the New State: The Case of Poland” ed. Carolin Kosuch, *Freethinkers in Europe: National and Transnational Secularities, 1789 1920s*. (Boston: De Gruyter, 2020).

¹⁶⁰ „Poezja narodowa a wersyfikacja esperancka,” *Myśl Niepodległa*, nr 366 (Warsaw: 30 December 1916), p. 816.

¹⁶¹ Ibid p.820

¹⁶² Karol Appel, “Mutermilch, Waclaw. W kwestji wyboru języka pomocniczego międzynarodowego. Review.” *Książka*, 15 October 1910, nr 10, p.397

efforts to veil his antisemitic rhetoric: he attributed Esperanto's popularity to the power of the "Jewish capital, led by the slogan 'Semites of the world, unite'".¹⁶³ In his view, "only an individual without a homeland and without an innate linguistic sense"¹⁶⁴ could possibly "spoil" other, national languages by melting them into Esperanto. While in Appel's opinion, the French word *revue* sounded "harmonious and sweet", Esperanto's equivalent, *revuo* was common and jargon-like. Appel's article not only summarises the aesthetic doubts the critics of the international language so often expressed, but it also singles out the next, perhaps the most pertinent reason for Esperanto's criticism: its Jewishness.

4.3 Jews, Bolsheviks, and freethinkers

Antisemitism haunted Esperanto from very early on. It was a well-known fact that the creator of Esperanto, Ludwik Zamenhof, was a Jew. In trying to sell Esperanto on an international stage that Jewishness had to be obscured. As Ulrich Lins observes, Zamenhof understood it very well himself and, although committed to working for the Jewish cause by promoting Esperanto and the ideas of the unity of mankind as expressed in the teachings of Homoranism and Hillelism, he never published anything that would openly discuss the language's role for the Jew.¹⁶⁵ Depending on the author's mood and political convictions, Zamenhof in Poland was presented on scale ranging from "our compatriot" or "a Polish doctor", to a more neutral "Varsovian", to the

¹⁶³ Ibid. p. 398.

¹⁶⁴ Ibid.

¹⁶⁵ Lins, *Dangerous Language*, p. 26.

blunt “son of Białystok’s ghetto”¹⁶⁶. He was mostly admired and lauded for his work, yet his origin, coupled by the fact that the language was meant to transcend national borders, activated almost automatic response and associations among contemporary Europeans.

In Poland, as we read in the previous part of this chapter, Esperanto was initially perceived as a threat to the stature of the Polish language. It was only later, when Polish language became legitimized, that the linguistic threat became territorial and existential. As Poland’s – and Europe’s fate was at stake, with many voices questioning the need for the creation of a Polish state, in 1915, two years prior to his death, Zamenhof delivered his *Appeal to diplomats*. In his speech, Zamenhof proposed something that could roughly resemble today’s European Union: a supra-european transnational entity, with its own, Pan-European court of justice, guaranteeing linguistic and ethnic equality to both “natural and naturalised”¹⁶⁷ citizens. He went even further to suggest “abolishing the racial names of the countries”¹⁶⁸ and replacing them with new constructs in Esperanto

(...) for the unfortunate name will not only seem to justify the most despicable interracial abuses in those countries of Eastern Europe where the races are mingled, but even in more civilized countries it will always warp the judgment of even the most right-minded citizens, ever perpetuating in them the belief and impression that

¹⁶⁶ To further explore the identities of Zamenhof, his view on Jewishness, nationalism, and humanity in general, please see Jagodzińska, Agnieszka (ed), *Ludwik Zamenhof wobec “kwestii żydowskiej”*. (Krakow / Budapest, 2012) and Künzli, Andreas, L.L. *Zamenhof (1859-1917): Esperanto, Hillelismus (Homaranismus) und die “jüdische Frage” in Ost- und Westeuropa*, (Wiesbaden: Otto Harrassowitz Verlag, 2010).

¹⁶⁷ Ludwik Zamenhof, *Appeal to Diplomats*, 1915

<http://www.autodidactproject.org/esperanto2010/zamenhof_diplomats.html> Accessed 10 August 2020.

¹⁶⁸ Ibid.

the country belongs only to that race whose name it bears, and that all its other races are but aliens there.¹⁶⁹

Unsurprisingly, Zamenhof's *Appeal* did not go down well in Poland. Aside from being called barbaric for accommodating different ethnicities and compared to "civilised" but ethnically sterile "western" nations, Poles felt betrayed in their attempts of resurrecting their statehood. "Myśl Niepodległa" published an entire article dissecting Zamenhof's speech. It was called treacherous and perfidious for craftily replacing the word *nation-nacio* by the word *tribe-gento*¹⁷⁰ and introducing the division into state, local and urban languages. This was clearly seen as an anti-Polish coup.

It is a subtle distinction, incomprehensible to anyone abroad, and introduced very skilfully and imperceptibly by a Polish Jew, who at home calls Russian the state language, Polish the local language, and a German jargon the language of our Jew-infested cities and towns.¹⁷¹

The article categorises Jews as a "psychological race" that notoriously advocates "formal evasions" in its religious scripts and accuses Zamenhof of supporting Jewish nationalism while

¹⁶⁹ Ibid.

¹⁷⁰ "O liście otwartym Dr Ludwika Zamenhofa do dyplomatów," *Myśl Niepodległa*, nr 305 (Warsaw: 18 April 1915) p. 163.

¹⁷¹ Ibid, pp. 163-164.

trying to erase all others. In the author's view, Zamenhof was not "an Aryan type of an inventor", as he was trying to attach an ideology, "a doctrine" to the language, rather than just focus on its practical application. Hillelism and Homoranism, the philosophies Zamenhof held dear, were both portrayed as "perverse and harmful" for discouraging patriotism and making the love of homeland look "disgusting".

After the Polish-Soviet War of 1919-1920, the spectre of communism, although temporarily chased away, became more real than ever. Due to a common notion that Jews aided the Bolsheviks during the war, Bolshevism and Judaism quickly became synonymous and enmeshed. Any organisations associated with internationalism, socialism or simply Jewishness were placed under exceptional scrutiny, including Esperanto clubs. One example is that of SAT, the a-national Esperanto organisation. The movement was famous for its strong left-wing, if not communist stance, and its founder, Adam Lanti, was a sworn anti-capitalist member of the French Communist Party, for whom Zamenhof's philosophy of tolerance was not good enough, as it did not offer social justice.¹⁷² In 1928 curriculars were sent to local police stations warning against the movement and presenting it as having a "disorganising and destructive"¹⁷³ position in the Esperanto movement. The document accused SAT of using the lack of clarity and purpose around Esperanto for its own nefarious means.

Antisemitism and unfounded suspicion against the Jews manifested itself on numerous other occasions. One such case involves "Espero" club in Lublin, which never came to exist, because the would-be members were all Jews. Having applied for a permission to start a new

¹⁷² Schor, *Bridge...* p.144.

¹⁷³ Archiwum Narodowe w Krakowie. Starostwo Grodzkie Krakowskie. Komenda Policji Pństwowej m. Krakowa. Sygnatura 724.

Esperanto club in Lublin, the petitioners, mostly Jewish intelligentsia, were carefully investigated and all proved to be of “a flawless moral conduct”¹⁷⁴, neither politically active nor belonging to any other questionable organisation. Despite this, their request was denied.

(...) I report that an initiative to start a new Esperanto organisation has been received from a group represented by Rubin Szolzon, Icek-Szmul Kuna, and Masza Kohn, all inhabitants of Lublin. Their attitude towards the Polish Esperanto Association of Lublin is negative, as it is in Polish hands, and is driven by Jewish nationalism. Besides, the financial side is here at stake, as the founders are looking for a source of income and only for these and no other reasons do they desire to start their own, /Jewish/ Esperanto club.¹⁷⁵

As we can see from the report above, Lublin authorities were clearly projecting their own vision and ethnic stereotypes surrounding Polish Jews, such as assumed hatred of all things Polish or the desire of financial gain.¹⁷⁶

¹⁷⁴ Archiwum Akt Nowych. Urząd Wojewódzki Lubelski. Działalność komunistyczna. 1928. Sygnatura 270/IV-13.

¹⁷⁵ Ibid.

¹⁷⁶ It is unsurprising that the sharpest observed form of anti-semitism in Polish Esperanto comes from Lublin. The city was, and perhaps still is a stronghold of Catholicism and Polish conservatism, and today is home to the biggest Catholic university in Poland - KUL (Katolicki Uniwersytet Lubelski). See Konrad Sadkowski, *Church, Nation, and State in Poland: Catholicism and National Identity Formation in the Lublin Region, 1918-1939.* (University of Michigan: ProQuest Dissertations Publishing, 1995) Accessed 17 September 2020. <<https://deepblue.lib.umich.edu/handle/2027.42/129726>>.

From its inception, reborn Poland was torn between two visions and leaders: the Poland of the Piasts and the Poland of the Jagiellons. On the one hand, the Chief of State, Józef Piłsudski, born in Lithuania and proudly identifying as *Litvak*, who famously compared the country to a pretzel: “fertile borderlands and nothing inside”, promoted the Jagiellonian vision, in which minorities co-existed peacefully, international connections were cultivated and valued, and the diverse nature of the land contributed to the power and position of the country in Europe. Piłsudski saw the different nations incorporated in the Polish state in civic, rather than ethnic terms. To him, all minorities: Jews, Ukrainians, Lithuanians, Belarussians could be of value as citizens.¹⁷⁷ On the other hand, Warsaw-born Roman Dmowski advocated the Piast vision of Poland: an ethnically monolithic national democracy, smaller, but homogenous and thus easier to manage and more loyal. Dmowski vision was directly based, if not copied after, the already established European nation-states, like Germany, with which, at the same time, Poland was in direct competition. In the mid-1930s, after the death of Józef Piłsudski, and with the dawn of his *sanacja* movement, a void was created: national democrats gained more power and, echoing neighbouring Germany, antisemitic rhetoric intensified. The radical, far-right National Radical Camp (ONR) emerged around mid-1930s, actively fighting minorities and the “Jewish-Bolshevik-plutocratic conspiracy.”¹⁷⁸ This did not bode well for neutral, transnational, tolerance-promoting movements like Esperanto.

The fragile new movement quickly became the target in a country where nationalism was on the rise. Its symbol, the green five-pointed star was compared to either the red Soviet star or the

¹⁷⁷ Patrice M. Dabrowski, “Uses and abuses of the Polish past by Józef Piłsudski and Roman Dmowski.” *The Polish Review*, vol. 56, no. 1/2, 2011, pp. 73–109.

¹⁷⁸ Qtd in Aristotle Kallis, *Genocide and Fascism: The Eliminationist Drive in Fascist Europe* (New York: Routledge, 2009) p. 125.

star of David.¹⁷⁹ The language was dubbed a tool of Bolshevism “at the service of Comintern”. In 1937, “Information bulletin: the truth about communism” published a list of all communist/socialist organisations in Europe to keep its readers alert to any potential danger and to help them distinguish the “good” Esperanto clubs from the “bad” ones. “It is understood that there are many Esperantists who have nothing to do with communism, just like there are sportsmen who know nothing of Sportintern”¹⁸⁰ the article concludes. “Nevertheless, Esperanto is an especially useful tool for the communications and the propaganda of Comintern, which communists use in Switzerland and elsewhere.”¹⁸¹

In the mainstream media, Esperanto, once an object of general curiosity, was being gradually demonised as a masonic tool of Jews and Communists, perfidious work of Comintern in Poland. *Dziennik Bydgoski* in its report from the Warsaw Esperanto Congress in 1937 was openly using offensive racial slurs such a “żydziak” or “żydostwo” and its author did little to conceal his open disgust at the thought of sitting next to people of other ethnicities.

Esperanto (...) is gaining many supporters, though not everybody knows whose political aims it serves. All of Nalewki (a Jewish district of Warsaw – author’s note) were in front of the Philharmonic Hall. A Jew upon a Jew. It seemed to us we were

¹⁷⁹ ”Gwiazdka Esperancka symbolem miłości i zgody,” *Dziennik Bydgoski*, nr 294 (Bydgoszcz: 23 Dec 1934) p. 12.

¹⁸⁰ ”Esperanto na usługach Kominternu,” *Biuletyn informacyjny: walka z komunizmem*, POK. R.1, 1937, Zeszyt 10, p. 318.

¹⁸¹ Ibid.

not in Warsaw but in Zurich at a Zionist congress. No wonder a large number of police and the ER services were at the ready.¹⁸²

By his silent endorsement of the police and ER presence, the author illustrates for us the growing spirit of violence and fascism-borne brutality of the social life in Poland and Europe in the late 1930s.¹⁸³ His attitude is confirmed when he expresses his loathing of the fact that the Congress members cheered for communist generals in Spain and wished death to General Franco, as well as by a Ukrainian Esperantist who dared to express hope for independent Ukraine.

In other news, a daily *ABC* paper listed a “seemingly innocent”¹⁸⁴ paper entitled *Esperanto for everyone* in its “Communist Press Review” section for daring to publish Boris Pilnyak’s novel and including advertisements of some Soviet publishing houses.¹⁸⁵ The other blacklisted publications on the same page included anti-clerical publications of the Freethinkers.

As Roberto Garvía observes, Esperanto quickly gained support among international Freethinkers who opposed organised religion and nationalism.¹⁸⁶ Polish freethinkers were not left behind in their appreciation of the new language. Its neutrality and rationality was so appealing that in 1929, they published their *Ilustrowana encyklopedia wolnomyślicielska* (Illustrated

¹⁸² “Niedziela Zjazdów,” *Dziennik Bydgoski*, nr 181 (Bydgoszcz, 10 August 1937) pp. 1-2.

¹⁸³ For the transnational nature of fascism, please see: Passmore, Kevin, ‘Fascism as a Social Movement in a Transnational Context’ in Stefan Berger, Holger Nehring (eds.), *The History of Social Movements in Global Perspective* (London: Palgrave Macmillan, 2017).

¹⁸⁴ “Którędy idzie robota wywrotowa? Przegląd prasy komunistycznej w polsce. ‘Esperanto dla wszystkich’”, *ABC*, nr 39 (Warsaw: 9 February 1934).

¹⁸⁵ *Ibid.*

¹⁸⁶ Garvía, *Esperanto...*, p. 120.

encyclopaedia of freethought) with a double front page: one in Polish and another one in Esperanto.¹⁸⁷ Here is what they wrote about Esperanto in their magazine, *Przyrodniczy pogląd na świat i życie*, a magazine dedicated to promoting science and reason:

(...) In this way, the living word, as well as the written word, fights superstition and frivolity, there is also no greater enemy for the supporters of the old, better times, like a book or a congregation. They take away their bread, gypsy bread, take away their power, expose their dirt and greed. (...) Esperanto is one of the best battering rams for the ultimate overthrow of stupidity, chauvinism and backwardness.¹⁸⁸

However, in a newly reconstructed country, where identities and loyalties were being tried and tested, internationalism and anti-clericalism were quickly judged as corrupt, aimed at weakening Polishness, associated with communism, and masterminded by Jews. Going through various Polish police archives, one notices that the files of Esperantists and freethinkers were often kept in the same folder.¹⁸⁹ Indeed, it is a fact that although Esperanto in Poland had perhaps the most neutral character of all European countries, many Esperantists identified themselves with the

¹⁸⁷ Wagner, *Secularity...*, p.147.

¹⁸⁸ Leopold Kronenberg, "Esperanto a postęp kulturalny ludzkości", *Przyrodniczy pogląd na świat i życie*, nr 3 (Kraków: March 1912) p. 21.

¹⁸⁹ For example: Archiwum Narodowe w Krakowie. Starostwo Grodzkie Krakowskie. Komenda Policji Państwowej m. Krakowa. Sygnatura 724.

progressive, liberal, and anti-clerical thought and were active on an international level in circles beyond Esperanto.

The most notable example perhaps is that of a renowned linguist, Jan Baudouin de Courtenay. He was an atheist, not afraid to publicly support minorities, oppose xenophobia and even state that “it is possible to Polish and German at the same time”¹⁹⁰ Another example includes Dr Emilian Loth, who was an active member of the Rotary Club. Even a bona fide charity organisation like Rotary was under scrutiny by Polish nationalist. A far-right publication “*Stalowy Miecz*” dedicated an entire article to the Rotarians, explaining that their charity work was just a cover for shaping young Polish professionals “in a Masonic fashion” orchestrated by “everybody knows who.”¹⁹¹

Freethinkers saw in Esperanto an opportunity to illuminate the masses and fight with oppression. Interestingly enough, as much as the nationalists fought with their ideas, the most concerned party, the Polish Catholic Church, decided to beat the freethinkers at their own game: they embraced Esperanto and used it to their own means.

Should we, Catholics, look with indifference at this world movement? Are we not terrified by the fact that the Esperanto movement is, so far, mostly in the hands of sectarians, freemasons, and communists? Don't we feel a blush of shame at the thought that the only Polish Esperanto monthly, published in Krakow, is

¹⁹⁰ Igor Belov, “Baudouin de Courtenay – The Anatomy of Language,” *Culture.pl* <<https://culture.pl/en/article/ baudouin-de-courtenay-the-anatomy-of-language>> Accessed 25 August 2020.

¹⁹¹ ”Ruch w interesie,” *Stalowy Miecz*, nr 15 (15 October 1936).

edited by Jews; that even the Maravites publish their propaganda magazine in Esperanto? The importance of Esperanto has already been recognized and used by the enemies of Catholicism for its nefarious, anti-religious purposes.

It is time for us to stand up to Masonic or Jewish actions, to inform the influential Esperanto press about Poland and Polish Catholicism, to follow the example of Catholics of other countries, to follow the example of our brothers in the Netherlands, where the entire episcopate became keenly interested in the subject of the international language.¹⁹²

The Catholic Church in Poland was indeed very open-minded and accepting towards the new language. Catholic Esperanto organisations were in existence and organised their own activities and summer camps. This clearly demonstrates that the very heart of Polish conservatism, the Catholic Church, was at ease with *lingvo internacia* and that the actual backlash against Esperanto was chiefly political and reflected the general rise of anti-semitism and nationalism in Europe.

4.4 The twilight of Esperanto

In 1937, a report came to the Warsaw Police Headquarters stating that during the International Esperanto Congress taking place that year, “communist and pornographic

¹⁹² Antoni Troszyński, “Katolicy a akcja esperancka,” *Pod znakiem Marji*, nr 7 (Kraków: April 1929) p 167.

publications”¹⁹³ were being distributed. As a result, the report recommended “the loosening of ties” between all public and military officials and Esperanto societies. As bizarre as this accusation might seem, it is important to point out that in the late 1930s Poland, pornography was not just deemed wrong for being universally immoral, vulgar, degrading or exploitative – it was very specifically depicted as a tool of communist propaganda used to aid the creation of a morally and spiritually devoid world, a world in which “a woman who loves her kids is nothing but a bitch, a female”¹⁹⁴ and where marriage, religion and family values are systemically annihilated. In other words, promoting a system which directly targeted traditional Polish values.

(...) Today’s cinema, theatre, books, newspapers, street and specialised publishing houses do communism invaluable favours. Even more so considering that an auxiliary current flows from the West, and not directly from Moscow. In Germany, the second most communised country after Russia, multiple nudist clubs have sprung up, aka. clubs for “free people”. Such clubs rent out gardens and forests where male and female members parade completely naked, without any covers. The photos of their frolics, in various poses, are album materials increasingly exported to Poland. Nearly every paper rack, kiosk, first-class bookstores in Warsaw (M. Arct, Polish Library, Military Bookstore) sell pornographic materials, generously illustrated, mostly French and German, and published predominantly by Jews in France and Germany.¹⁹⁵

¹⁹³ Archiwum Akt Nowych. *Komenda Główna Policji Państwowej w Warszawie*. 9 November 1937. Sygnatura 362.

¹⁹⁴ *Walka z Bolszewizmem : miesięcznik bezpartyjny i niezależny, poświęcony obronie Polski przed bolszewicko-komunistycznym najazdem*. 1931, nr 34 p.10.

¹⁹⁵Ibid p.11.

By drawing a parallel between the nudist clubs in Germany,¹⁹⁶ communism and pornography, and linking them all to Esperanto, the report yet again painted a well-known picture of foreign influence penetrating the Polish moral tissue. Such influence would inadvertently pour into Poland from abroad, together with modernity, technology, media and internationalism. Paradoxically, while Polish far-right media depicted Germany as some sort of a semi-communist, liberal paradise, with nudists parading au naturelle in the countryside, German Esperantists were being persecuted for almost exactly the same reasons. The Nazis, too, saw in Esperanto a threat incongruent with their singular vision of *Nationalsozialismus* and “a sign of insufficient patriotism”¹⁹⁷ leading to the “weakening of the essential values of the national heritage”.¹⁹⁸

In this atmosphere of thickening nationalisms and permanent suspicion, Esperanto’s fate was doomed. As Steffen and Kohlrausch point out in their article describing the rise and fall of two Polish experts¹⁹⁹, after 1918, Poland was reliant on specialised knowledge to rise from the ashes of WWI and reinvent itself as an independent nation. This relationship between experts and the state, however, was tense, since these internationally educated, science-led, multilingual specialists, who once constituted the core of the Esperanto movement, would drift away from the

¹⁹⁶ *Lebensreform* was a movement in Germany aimed at “returning to Nature” and included various outdoor activities, including nudism. As John Alexander William argues in *Turning to Nature in Germany: Hiking, Nudism, and Conservation, 1900-1940*. (Stanford University Press, 2007), the movement was a way through which a troubled nation sought to escape and solve its problems.

¹⁹⁷ Lins, *Dangerous Language*, p. 93.

¹⁹⁸ *Deutsche Wissenschaft, Erziehung und Volksbildung* 1 (1935), 10 (20 May), official part, p. 228 qtd in Lins, p.110.

¹⁹⁹ Katrin Steffen, and Martin Kohlrausch, “The Limits and Merits of Internationalism: Experts, the State and the International Community in Poland in the First Half of the Twentieth Century”. *European Review of History: Revue Européenne d’histoire* 16, no. 5 (2009) <<https://doi.org/10.1080/13507480903262728>>.

traditionally understood notion of Polishness, had multiple identities and their loyalty could not be taken for granted. In the late 1930s, transnational networks, created by hopeful Polish patriots to collaborate and gain expertise, became highly mistrusted. In this context, Esperanto became more vulnerable than ever and could very quickly and almost effortlessly be vilified as yet another foreign export, Jewish, Bolshevik or Masonic conspiracy, a grave threat to regained independence and traditional Polish values, aided and abetted by “progress”.

4.5 Conclusion

In reborn Poland, Esperanto, a movement which was a precursor of globalisation as we know it today and which, as Young Kim argues, laid foundations of what we consider today a global identity,²⁰⁰ was to its contemporaries a sort of Rorschach test, which projected the existing worries, fears and insecurities of the pre-WWII Polish society. Its neutrality was for many too suspicious to accept in a new, fragile state, despite efforts to combat prejudice from the movement leaders. Attacks on Esperanto, which were inadvertently related to the Judeo-Bolshevik, internationalist “threat” were not dissimilar from the accusations Esperanto faced in other European states. Yet, in multicultural Poland, as opposed to more established, homogenous nation-states, these attacks were directly related to the political debate taking place on the future and nature of the country and reflected the moods of the Polish society and its various definitions of

²⁰⁰ Young S. Kim, “Constructing a Global Identity. The Role of Esperanto” in Boli, John and George M. Thomas (eds), *Constructing World Culture. International Nongovernmental Organizations since 1875*, Stanford: Stanford University Press, 1999, pp. 127-148.

what new Poland should look like. As the new country was presented with a choice between the value of the transnational connections and protecting its essence, Esperanto would be a target of paradoxical if not paranoid fears and attacks, which would, in time, ruin its reputation as a neutral language facilitating international communication.

At the same time, however, just like in the rest of Europe, the criticism of Esperanto intensified in the mid- to late 1930s, which indicates that the rise of fascism on the continent affected Polish audiences. This proves fascism was indeed, a social and transnational movement²⁰¹, which permeated the Polish society, despite or maybe because of its multiculturalism and efforts at modernisation. Attempts were made to separate Esperanto as a purely utilitarian tool from the “ideology” which it was surrounded by, yet this often proved to be an impossible task. The spectre of communism and the Jewish roots of its inventor meant that Esperanto had to fight off vicious attacks and constantly prove its neutrality and good intentions.

²⁰¹ Passmore, Kevin, ‘Fascism as a Social Movement in a Transnational Context’ in Stefan Berger, Holger Nehring (eds.), *The History of Social Movements in Global Perspective* (London: Palgrave Macmillan, 2017): 579-617.

CONCLUSION

Arthur Schopenhauer famously said, “All truth passes through three stages. First, it is ridiculed. Second, it is violently opposed. Third, it is accepted as being self-evident.” In Esperanto’s case, it certainly went through stage one and two. At first, it was seen as a benign idiocy, a ridiculous invention which stood no chance of success. As the movement grew in strength, Esperanto’s enemies slowly raised their heads, and attacked it until it was vilified as “a dangerous language.” Yet, it never found itself fully accepted. This very fact, that a simple language can prove so controversial, proves the power languages have in the societies around the world and their importance in shaping our identities and loyalties.

In pre-war Poland, the issue of determining the nation’s identity was the ultimate question, to which there was no single answer. In this context, Esperanto, being mostly in the hands of a narrow group of scientists, artists, idealists, and intellectuals, had a huge potential but limited impact. The elite Esperantists were faced with the daunting task of coupling progress with patriotism, which, provided Polish historical context at the time, proved to be a major challenge. Esperantists in Poland had to navigate issues which were foreign to their counterparts in more established, ethnically and linguistically almost monolithic nation-states, such as France or Germany. In multicultural Poland, it was extra difficult to toe the line of Polishness, which had to be proven at every opportunity to avoid accusations of having a “foreign” agenda. For this reason, Polish Esperantists would have to distance themselves from the philosophy of Homoranism, as defined by Zamenhof. Another question was how to appeal to impoverished, undereducated masses of peasantry and townsfolk, the problems inherited after 123 years of partitions and anti-Polish politics of the neighbouring empires. In addition, a relationship had to be established

between the “mainstream Esperantists” and other, minor Esperanto clubs in Poland, which were not Poland – oriented in their agenda. Official standpoints had to be made clear to allow Esperantists to declare their loyalty to their country and distance themselves from any notion of pan-European or Marxist loyalty. Finally, like in the rest of Europe, Esperanto had to stand up to home-grown fascism and fight off ridiculous accusations, racism and xenophobia.

This thesis is the first of its kind to examine the use of Esperanto for the promotion of nationhood and statehood, the topic largely overlooked by the existing research predominantly focused on Esperanto as an a-national movement. My research proves that Esperanto not only served international movements such as Marxism or anarchism but was more often than not a platform for downtrodden nations to showcase their nationhood. Esperanto offered these “small nations” a unique chance to define themselves in the face of oppression and to avoid being forgotten or lost between the European imperial giants. In this sense, my thesis serves a springboard for future research on the links between nationalism and Esperanto, for example in Ireland, Scotland, Catalonia and many others.

Finally, my thesis is also significant in modern day Poland, where the debate surrounding Białystok and Zamenhof is more vivid than ever. Even though Esperanto was, in 2014, listed as Polish intangible cultural heritage,²⁰² it is still looked at through the lens of Homoranism by its conservative ultra-nationalist opposers, who call it a useless utopia.²⁰³ My thesis contributes to this

²⁰² Niematerialne Dziedzictwo Kulturowe. Narodowy Instytut Dziedzictwa. *Krajowa lista niematerialnego dziedzictwa kulturowego*.

<http://niematerialne.nid.pl/Dziedzictwo_niematerialne/Krajowa_inwentaryzacja/Krajowa_lista_NDK>. Accessed 12 February 2020.

²⁰³ ”Zamenhof? Utopie trzeba tepić. Popisy radnego Wasilewskiego.” *Gazeta Wyborcza Białystok*. 24 October 2016.

<<https://bialystok.wyborcza.pl/bialystok/1,35241,20880804,zamenhof-utopie-trzeba-tepic-popisy-radnego-wasilewskiego.html?disableRedirects=true>> Accessed 10 June 2020.

argument, proving that in its history, Esperanto was used to promote the idea of a nation as much as it was used to promote internationalism.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

6.1 Archival Sources

ŁÓDŹ

Archiwum Państwowe w Łodzi. Archiwum Dr Emiliana Lotha Inżyniera Chemika w Pabianicach. *Przemówienia na uroczystościach, zebraniach, odczytach, notatki z podróży zagranicznych*. 1914-1939. Sygnatura 8.

Archiwum Państwowe w Łodzi. *Pisma przychodzące do Sekcji Szkolnej – prośby o pomoc finansową instytucji i stowarzyszeń oświatowych na cele oświaty, kursy biblioteczne i esperanto*. Sygnatura 182/136.

Pfeiffer, Włodimierz. *Kronika Esperantystów Łódzkich*. Biblioteka Uniwersytetu Łódzkiego. 5005/2.

KRAKÓW

Archiwum Narodowe w Karkowie. *Korespondencja uczennic szkoły z młodzieżą z miasta Växjö (w języku esperanto)*. Sygnatura LGK 207.

Archiwum Narodowe w Krakowie. Starostwo Grodzkie Krakowskie. *Komenda Policji Państwowej m. Krakowa*. Sygnatura 724.

Narodowe Archiwum Cyfrowe. Image: *Zofia Batycka*, 1932. Sygnatura 1-K-7448 <<https://audiovis.nac.gov.pl/obraz/73847/>>.

WARSAW

Archiwum Akt Nowych. Ambasada RP w Waszyngtonie. Sygnatura 1663.

Archiwum Akt Nowych. Archiwum Związku Harcerstwa Polskiego. *Esperanto [korespondencja w sprawie propagowania Esperanto]*. Report "Do Naczelnika Harcerstwa Polskiego", 13 November 1931. Sygnatura 1481.

Archiwum Akt Nowych. Komenda Główna Policji Państwowej w Warszawie. *Sprawy Osobowe funkcjonariusz Policji Państwowej. Zarządzenia, instrukcje*. 9 November 1937. Sygnatura 362.

Archiwum Akt Nowych. Ministerstwo Spraw Zagranicznych. 10 July 1926. Sygnatura 7192.

Archiwum Akt Nowych. Ministerstwo Spraw Zagranicznych. Odo Bujwid's Letter. 14 April 1934. Sygnatura 7207.

Archiwum Akt Nowych. Ministerstwo Spraw Zagranicznych. 29 April 1934. Sygnatura 7207.

Archiwum Akt Nowych. Ministerstwo Spraw Zagranicznych. Odo Bujwid's letter, 1 September 1936. Sygnatura 2975.

Archiwum Akt Nowych. Ministerstwo Spraw Zagranicznych. Poselstwo RP w Wiedniu. *List w sprawie światowego zjazdu esperantystów*. 3 January 1935. Sygnatura 2975.

Archiwum Akt Nowych. Poselstwo RP w Sztokholmie. *Kongres Esperantystów w Warszawie*. 16 August 1927. Sygnatura 53.

Archiwum Akt Nowych. Urząd Wojewódzki Lubelski. *Działalność komunistyczna*. 1928. Sygnatura 270/IV-13.

6.2 Primary sources:

Appel, Karol. "Mutermilch, Waclaw. W kwestji wyboru języka pomocniczego międzynarodowego. Review." *Książka*. Nr 10 (Warsaw: 15 October 1910).

"Czy warto uczyć się esperanta?" *Silacz. Dodatek do nr. 7 „Gazety Robotniczej.”* (Warsaw: 10 January 1926).

Deutsche Wissenschaft, Erziehung und Volksbildung 1 (1935), 10 (20 May).

"Esperanto." *The Review of Reviews*. Ed. William Thomas Stead. Vol. 39. (London: January-June 1909).

"Esperanto na usługach Kominternu." *Biuletyn informacyjny: walka z komunizmem*. POK. R.1, 1937, Zeszyt 10.

"Gwiazdka Esperancka symbolem miłości i zgody." *Dziennik Bydgoski*. Nr 294 (Bydgoszcz: 23 December 1934).

"Gwiazdy i gwiazdory filmu polskiego." *Pomocniczy Język Światowy*. Nr 8-9 (Kraków: August-September 1931).

"Język handlowy oraz próby języka międzynarodowego," *Dźwignia Przemysłowo-Handlowa Ilustrowana*, 15 June 1987, nr 12.

"Kącik Esperancki." *Robotnik*. Nr 299. (Warsaw: 31 October 1927).

Kongresoj database. Dr Bernhard Struck.

Kronenberg, Leopold. "Esperanto a postęp kulturalny ludzkości." *Przyrodniczy pogląd na świat i życie*. Nr 3 (Kraków: March 1912).

“Którędy idzie robota wywrotowa? Przegląd prasy komunistycznej w polsce. ‘Esperanto dla wszystkich.’” *ABC*. Nr 39 (Warsaw: 9 February 1934).

Łodzianin, Nr 37 (Łódź: 10 September 1922).

”Niebezpieczne Esperanto.” *Nowy Kurjer Łódzki*. Nr 171 (Łódź, 28 July 1913).

”Niedziela Zjazdów.” *Dziennik Bydgoski*. Nr 181 (Bydgoszcz, 10 August 1937).

”O liście otwartym Dr Ludwika Zamenhofa do dyplomatów,” *Myśl Niepodległa*, nr 305 (Warsaw: 18 April 1915).

”Poezja narodowa a wersyfikacja esperancka.” *Myśl Niepodległa*. Nr 366 (Warsaw: 30 December 1916).

Pola Esperanristo (PE). (1906-1937)

Parker, Patrick. ‘Mother tongues and Esperanto’, *Tutmonda Espero*, No. 17 (May 1909).

”Pierwszy Wszechpolski Kongres Esperantystów.” *Robotnik*. Nr 151. (Warsaw 6 June 1922).

Pujulà i Vallès, Frederic. “Pri... escepto, kiun oni faris en Antverpeno por katalunoj.” *Kataluna Esperantisto*. No. 24 (March 1912). <[https://bibliotekoj.org/literaturamondo/ke1/KE024\(1912-03\).pdf](https://bibliotekoj.org/literaturamondo/ke1/KE024(1912-03).pdf)>.

”Ruch w interesie,” *Stalowy Miecz*, nr 15 (15 October 1936).

”Socjalizm ośmiesz religię katolicką i szerzy komunizm.” *Robotnik Katolicki*. Nr 6 (Tarnów: 1 November 1938).

Troszyński, Antoni. ”Katolicy a akcja esperancka.” *Pod znakiem Marji*. Nr 7 (Kraków: April 1929).

Walka z Bolszewizmem : miesięcznik bezpartyjny i niezależny, poświęcony obronie Polski przed bolszewicko-komunistycznym najazdem. 1931, nr 34.

”IV wszechpolski kongres esperantystów w Łodzi.” *Łodzianin*. Nr 40 (Łódź: 27 September 1930).

”V Kongres robotniczej międzynarodówki esperanckiej.” *Łodzianin*. Nr 34 (Łódź: 22 August 1925).

6.3 Secondary literature

Belov, Igor. “Baudouin de Courtenay – The Anatomy of Language.” *Culture.pl* <<https://culture.pl/en/article/ baudouin-de-courtenay-the-anatomy-of-language>> Accessed 25 August 2020.

Bhabha, Homi. *The Location of Culture* (New York: Routledge, 1994).

Blanke, Richard. “The Polish Role in the Origin of Kulturkampf in Prussia.” *Canadian Slavonic Papers / Revue Canadienne des Slavistes*. Vol. 25, No. 2 (June 1983).

Broszat, Martin. *Zweihundert Jahre deutsche Polenpolitik*, (München: München Ehrenwirth, 1963).

Cieślukowska, Agnieszka J. ”Edmund Libański i jego lwowskie czasopismo ‘Przemysłowiec’ [The Industrialist] (1903–1910).” *Rocznik Historii Prasy Polskiej*. Tom XIX, Zeszyt 3, 2016.

Chu, Winson. "The 'Lodzermensch': From Cultural Contamination to Marketable Multiculturalism." *Germany, Poland and Postmemorial Relations: In Search of a Livable Past*. Ed. Kopp, Kristin, and Niżyńska, Joanna. (London: Palgrave Macmillan, 2012).

Chwalba, Andrzej. *Historia Polski 1795-1918*, (Kraków: Wydawnictwo Literackie, 2000).

Corrsin, Stephen D. "Language Use in Cultural and Political Change in Pre-1914 Warsaw: Poles, Jews, and Russification." *The Slavonic and East European Review*, vol. 68, no. 1, 1990.

Dabrowski, Patrice, M. "Uses and abuses of the Polish past by Józef Piłsudski and Roman Dmowski." *The Polish Review*, vol. 56, no. 1/2, 2011, pp. 73–109.

Davies, Norman. *God's Playground. A History of Poland* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1981).

Dziewanowski, Marian Kamil. *Poland in the twentieth century* (New York: Columbia University Press, 1977).

Dobrzyński, Roman. *Ulica Zamenhofa* (Bielsko-Biała: KLEKS, 2003).

Dobrzyński, Roman. *Zamenhof in Warsaw* (Białystok: Białystok Cultural Centre, 2019).

Dvorak, Anna. *A Hidden Immigration: The Geography of Polish-Brazilian Cultural Identity*. (Los Angeles: UCLA, 2013).

"Esperanto". *The Review of Reviews* ed. William Thomas Stead. Vol. 39 (London: January-June 1909).

Garvía, Roberto. *Esperanto and Its Rivals. The Struggle for and International Language* (Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 2015).

Gajzler, Andrzej Maria. "Organizacja Młodzieży Towarzystwa Uniwersytetu Robotniczego 1923—1936." *Prace Monograficzne nr 162* (Kraków: Wydawnictwo Naukowe WSP, 1993).

Gierszewska, Barbara. "Inżynier Edmund Libański: popularyzator nauki i techniki we Lwowie w początkach XX wieku." *Kwartalnik Historii Nauki i Techniki* 49/2, 2004.

Giertych, Jędrzej. *In Defence of My Country* (London: Publications of the Roman Dmowski Society, 1981).

Golec, Józef. *Słownik Biograficzny Esperantystów Polskich* (Cieszyn: Oficyna Joseph Golec, 2010).

Greig, Jodie C. *The Sandbox of History: Nationality, Sexuality, and the Historical Impulse in Contemporary Polish LGBTQ Culture* (Ann Arbor: University of Michigan, 2016) <https://deepblue.lib.umich.edu/bitstream/handle/2027.42/133479/jcgreig_1.pdf?isAllowed=y&sequence=1>. Accessed June 2020.

Hagen, William W. *Germans, Poles, and Jews: The Nationality Conflict in the Prussian East, 1772-1914*. (Chicago-London: University of Chicago Press, 1980).

Heller, Wendy. *Lidia: The Life of Lidia Zamenhof Daughter of Esperanto* (Oxford: George Ronald, 1985).

Hroch, Miroslav. *Social Preconditions of National Revival in Europe: A Comparative Analysis of the Social Composition of Patriotic Groups Among the Smaller European Nations* (New York: Columbia University Press, 2000).

Jagodzińska, Agnieszka. *Ludwik Zamenhof wobec kwestii żydowskiej* (Kraków, Budapest: Austeria, 2012).

Kim, Young S. "Constructing a Global Identity. The Role of Esperanto" in Boli, John and George M. Thomas (eds). *Constructing World Culture. International Nongovernmental Organizations since 1875* (Stanford: Stanford University Press, 1999).

Komorowska, Hanna. "Analyzing Linguistic Landscapes. A Diachronic Study of Multilingualism in Poland". *Teaching and Learning in Multilingual contexts: Sociolinguistic and Educational Perspectives*. Eds. Otwinowska, A. and de Angelis, G. (Bristol: Multilingual Matters, 2014).

Korzhenkov, Alexander. *Zamenhof. The Life, Works and Ideas of the Author of Esperanto* (New York: Mondial, 2009).

Kronenberg, Leopold. "Esperanto a postęp kulturalny ludzkości." *Przyrodniczy pogląd na świat i życie*. March 1912, nr 3.

Kubera, Jacek. "Polska 'piastowska' vs 'jagiellońska'. Odmienność wizji relacji z Niemcami jako determinanta poglądów na polską politykę zagraniczną." *Acta Politica Polonica* nr 4/2016 (38).

Künzli, Andreas. *L.L. Zamenhof (1859-1917): Esperanto, Hillelismus (Homaranismus) und die "jüdische Frage" in Ost- und Westeuropa* (Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz Verlag, 2010).

Lins, Ulrich. *Dangerous Language: Esperanto under Hitler and Stalin* (Bonn: Palgrave Macmillan, 2016).

Loew, Peter Oliver. *Danzig: Biographie einer Stadt*. (München: Verlag C. H. Beck, 2011).

Mayer, Emil. *Esperanto i jego zadania* (Kraków: Juna Esperantisto, 1934).

Niematerialne Dziedzictwo Kulturowe. Narodowy Instytut Dziedzictwa. Krajowa lista niematerialnego dziedzictwa kulturowego.

<http://niematerialne.nid.pl/Dziedzictwo_niematerialne/Krajowa_inwentaryzacja/Krajowa_lista_NDK>. Accessed 12 February 2020.

Orzeszkowa, Eliza. *Kilka słów o kobietach* (Lviv: A. J. O. Rogosz, 1873).

Passmore, Kevin. "Fascism as a Social Movement in a Transnational Context" in Stefan Berger, Holger Nehring (eds.). *The History of Social Movements in Global Perspective* (London: Palgrave Macmillan, 2017).

Privat, Edmond. *Vivo de Zamenhof* (London: Brita Esperanto Asocio, 1920).

Pola Esperanto-Junularo, "Statut Polskiego Związku Esperantystów" <<http://pej.pl/pl/onas/dokumenty/statut-polskiego-zwiazku-esperantystow/>> Accessed 12 December 2019.

"Powstał pomnik młodego Zamenhofa." *Gazeta Wyborcza Białystok*. 11th April 2019.

Prizel, Ilya. *National Identity and Foreign Policy: Nationalism and Leadership in Poland, Russia and Ukraine*. (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1998).

Reta Vortaro <<http://www.reta-vortaro.de/revo/art/kabe.html>> Accessed 1 March 2020.

Romaniuk, Zbigniew, "Esperantyści na terenie powiatu bielskiego do 1939 roku." *Bielski Almanach Historyczny* (Bielsk Podlaski: Fundacja Ochrony Dziedzictwa Ziemi Bielskiej, 2017).

Rysak, Leszek. "Początki Harcerstwa." *Biuletyn Instytutu Pamięci Narodowej*. Nr 5/6/2010 <http://ipn.gov.pl/__data/assets/pdf_file/0018/62550/1-24736.pdf> Accessed March 2020.

Sadkowski, Konrad. *Church, Nation, and State in Poland: Catholicism and National Identity Formation in the Lublin Region, 1918-1939.* (University of Michigan: ProQuest Dissertations Publishing, 1995) <<https://deepblue.lib.umich.edu/handle/2027.42/129726>>. Accessed 17 September 2020.

Sewruk, Piotr. „Jedyny taki uniwersytet w Lublinie. Słuchacze głównie ze środowiska proletariackiego, ponad połowa bezrobotna.” *Gazeta Wyborcza* (Lublin: 30 March 2018).

Shamborovsky, Gregory. (translated by Areta Kovalska). “Zofia Batycka: The Lvivian Who Became Miss Polonia and a Famous Film Actress.” *Forgotten Galicia*. 3 July 2018.

<<https://forgottengalicia.com/zofia-batycka-lvivian-became-miss-polonia-and-famous-film-actress>>. Accessed March 2020.

Shor, Esther. *Bridge of Words* (New York: Metropolitan Books Henry Holt and Company, 2016).

Siemiatycki, Myer. “Why Is the Great Poet Tuwim Beloved by Poles, Yet Forgotten by Jews?” *The Jerusalem Post* | *JPost.com*. 24 Dec. 2019.

Steffen, Katrin, and Martin Kohlrausch. ‘The Limits and Merits of Internationalism: Experts, the State and the International Community in Poland in the First Half of the Twentieth Century’. *European Review of History: Revue Européenne d’histoire* 16, no. 5 (2009) <<https://doi.org/10.1080/13507480903262728>>. Accessed December 2019.

Trenkler, Carsten, and Nikolaus Wolf. “Economic Integration across Borders: The Polish Interwar Economy 1921-1937.” *European Review of Economic History*, vol. 9, no. 2, 2005.

Troszyński, Antoni. ”Katolicy a akcja esperancka.” *Pod znakiem Marji*. Nr 7: April 1929.

Tycner, Adam. ”Cyrylica nad Wisłą.” *Rzeczpospolita*. 19 May 2012 <<https://www.rp.pl/artukul/876299-Cyrylica-nad-Wisla.html>> Accessed 10 March 2020.

Wagner, Barbara. “Secularity in the New State: The Case of Poland” ed. Carolin Kosuch, *Freethinkers in Europe: National and Transnational Secularities, 1789 1920s*. Boston: De Gruyter, 2020.

Wandachowicz, Benedykt. "Włodzimierz Pfeiffer – kreatywny księgarz i dokumentalista." *BIBiK Biuletyn Informacji Bibliotecznych i Kulturalnych Wojewódzkiej i Miejskiej Biblioteki Publicznej w Łodzi*. Nr 10 (Łódź: 19 September 2011) <http://skany.wbp.lodz.pl/pliki/bibik/bibik_123/bibik_123.pdf>. Accessed March 2020.

Wandycz, Piotr Stefan. *The Lands of Partitioned Poland, 1795-1918*. E-book, Seattle: University of Washington Press, 1984, p.22. <https://hdl-handle-net.ezproxy.st-andrews.ac.uk/2027/heb.05069>. Accessed 26 Sep 2020.

Weeks, Theodore R. Nation and State in Late Imperial Russia. *Nationalism and Russification on the Western Frontier, 1863-1914*. (DeKalb, Ill.: Northern Ill. Univ. Press, 1996).

William, John Alexander. *Turning to Nature in Germany: Hiking, Nudism, and Conservation, 1900-1940*. (Stanford University Press, 2007).

Wilson, Leigh. *Modernism and Magic – experiments with spiritualism, theosophy and the occult* (Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2013).

Wnęk, Jan. "Problemy polskiego szkolnictwa zaboru pruskiego i rosyjskiego na kartach 'Szkoły' 1868-1914." *Biuletyn Historii Wychowania* (Poznań: Adam Mickiewicz University, 2019).

Zamenhof, Ludwik. *Appeal to Diplomats*. 1915. <http://www.autodidactproject.org/esperanto2010/zamenhof_diplomats.html> Accessed 10 August 2020.

"Zamenhof? Utopie trzeba tępić. Popisy radnego Wasilewskiego." *Gazeta Wyborcza Białystok*. 24 October 2016. <<https://bialystok.wyborcza.pl/bialystok/1,35241,20880804,zamenhof-utopie-trzeba-tepic-popisy-radnego-wasilewskiego.html?disableRedirects=true>> Accessed 10 June 2020.

Żelazny, Walter. *Ludwik Zamenhof* (Kraków: Nomos, 2012).

Żelazny, Walter. "Ludwik Zamenhof – kosmopolita swojego narodu." *Jewish History Quarterly*.

Ed. Jan Doktor et al. Vol 4 (Warsaw: Jewish Historical Institute, December 2002).